

A first annotated checklist of corticioid and polypore basidiomycetes of the Caucasus region

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Abstract. This is the first combined checklist of corticioid and polypore species from the territories in the Caucasus region, including Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russian Caucasus, NE Turkey, and N–NW Iran. Altogether 389 corticioid and 246 polypore species are known from the area, 74 of which are reported as new to the entire region. Each record includes literature references, and, when available, selected unpublished specimens deposited in herbaria or collected recently are listed. The distribution of each species in the Caucasian countries is summarized, and brief notes are provided for some species. Finally, a table and a diagram representing the number of corticioids and polypores and the ratio of these in each country are provided. The checklist aims to serve as a baseline for more detailed studies of wood-inhabiting basidiomycetes in the Caucasus region. The importance of this catalogue for fungal conservation is also mentioned.

Key words: aphylloroid fungi, biodiversity, hotspot, polypore:corticioid ratio, Red List

Introduction

Although the precise physical delimitation of the Caucasus is rather controversial, it can be generally regarded as an integrated area, within which many biota have a shared history. High biological and landscape diversity, and the occurrence of two Pleistocene refugia, i.e. Colchis in Georgia (Gruziya) and Turkey, and Hyrcan in Iran and partly in Azerbaijan, are responsible for the area being designated as one of 25 hotspots of biodiversity, and included among the 200 Ecoregions of the world (Zazanashvili *et al.* 1999). About one fourth of the vascular plants are endemic to the area, which represents at least one of “the highest level of endemism in the temperate world” (Kremer *et al.* 2001).

Vascular plants of the Caucasus are quite well studied and numerous publications are available. Holubec and Křivka (2006) outlined the history of botanical explorations in the area and also mentioned the important treatments of the floras. Recently a throughout account of the Caucasus flora under the *Caucasian Flora Conspectus* is being prepared (see Takhtajan 2003, 2006). In comparison, cryptogams, and especially macrofungi, have received less attention and are in need of more detailed study.

This background provided the incentive to integrate the available data concerning the two important life forms of aphylloroid macrofungi, i.e. polypores and corticioids, in the Caucasus region, in order to draw a preliminary sketch of Caucasian wood-inhabiting fungal diversity.

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Fig. 1. The geographical area covered by the checklist

Major fungal floras or articles dealing with taxa in our focus in the Caucasian countries are e.g. Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986) and Bondartseva (1998) covering mainly Russia, Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971) for Armenia, Nakhutsrishvili (1986) for Georgia, Hallenberg (1981) for Iran, and Doğan *et al.* (2005) for Turkey. Additionally here are numerous articles and other publications which are listed in the reference section.

A vital prerequisite for taxonomic monographs and revisions is information on names that have been used. This checklist will facilitate the preparation of taxonomic treatments of Caucasian wood-inhabiting fungi. Another aim is conservation and facilitating the compilation of lists of endangered and threatened organisms (Red Lists). Wood-inhabiting fungi are important components of biodiversity, especially in forests and woodlands. Only a few wood-inhabiting fungi are included in the Red Data Books of countries in the Caucasus, e.g. a preliminary fungal Red List has been proposed for Armenia (see Nanaghulyan 2002, 2006). Krever *et al.* (2002) attempted to summarize data on rare and endangered fungal species appearing in the Red Data Books of the Caucasian countries. Except for the 11 fungi in the Red Data Book of Russia, they presented no data from other countries. Only three of the listed fungi were wood-inhabiting (polypores). To accomplish this aim properly, it is necessary to have a checklist for the area. Furthermore, to reach any conclusions about the composition and origin of the wood-mycota of the area and the nature of its relationships with other areas, basic knowledge of the occurrences of taxa and a compiled checklist are essential.

The area of the checklist

The Caucasus region is known as an intersection between Europe and Asia, with the Black Sea in the West and the Caspian Sea in the East. It consists of Georgia (including Abkhazia, Adjara and South Ossetia), Armenia, Azerbaijan (including Nakhichevan), the southernmost European parts of the Russian Federation (Russian Caucasus or North Caucasus), North-East Turkey, and North- to North-West Iran. Russian Caucasus refers to the Russian territories between the Sea of Azov, the Black Sea and the Caspian Sea, including Chechnia, Dagestan, Ingushetia, Kabardino-Balkaria, Karachayev-Cherkessia, North Ossetia-Alania, Krasnodar krai and Stavropol krai. However, the boundaries of the Southern part of the Caucasus (Transcaucasus) are subject to controversy. The administrative delimitations of the area exclude Iran and Turkey (e.g. Krever *et al.* 2001; Takhtajan 2003). Here we adopt a physio-phytogeographical approach, with a few modifications for checklist purposes. Firstly the major phytogeographical classifications concerning the area, e.g. Meusel *et al.* (1964–1992), Zohary (1973), Hedge & Wendelbo (1978), Takhtajan (1986), Browicz (1984–1988), and relevant information applied by, for example, Noroozi *et al.* (2008), were consulted. The boundaries of country provinces were then taken into account in order to make the checklist more practical. Therefore, from Turkey the provinces in the Mid to Eastern Black Sea region and in the upper Anatolian plateau are included: Sinop, Samsun, Amsaya, Ordu, Tokat, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Bayburt, Trabzon, Rize, Artvin, Ardahan, Kars, Erzurum, Iğdir, and Ağrı. From Iran the following provinces in the North and North-West of the country are included: Golestan, Mazandaran, Gilan, Ardabil, northern East Azerbaijan, and northern West Azerbaijan (Fig. 1).

Material and methods

The checklist consists of literature records (L) and examined specimens (E). Records were traced in available lists of fungi, floras, monographs, revisions and recent taxonomic, phylogenetic, and systematic treatments of the taxa concerned. Specimens were examined from the material deposited in the herbaria GB, TAA, H, S, and SVER. Moreover, collections made by Ghobad-Nejhad in 2005–2008 from Iran, by Hallenberg during 1989–1996 and 2008 from the Russian Caucasus, Turkey, and Iran, and by Kotiranta in 2003 from the Russian Caucasus were examined, and are selectively included in the checklist. Material of these collections is deposited in the herbaria GB, IRAN, H, and/or the reference herbarium of the respective collector. No attempt was made to re-examine the original material of the literature records. Whenever possible, we tried to find support for the records from recent collections.

Specimens were studied in 5 % potassium hydroxide (KOH), Melzer's reagent (IKI) and Cotton Blue in lactic acid (CB), using light and/or phase contrast microscopy. The abbreviation CWD stands for coarse woody debris.

The concept of corticioids generally follows *Corticaceae of Northern Europe* (Eriksson & Ryvarden 1973, 1975, 1976; Eriksson *et al.* 1978, 1981, 1984; Hjortstam *et al.* 1987, 1988; see also Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* 2008), and that of polypores mostly follows Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1993, 1994) and Niemelä (2005, 2008). *Schizophyllum* Fr. (including *S. amplum* (Lév.) Nakasone) and heterobasidioid taxa, as treated by, for example, Roberts (1999), are not included. Names under *Polypilus* mentioned by Gvritshvili *et al.* (2007) were omitted. For nomenclature and accepted names the public databases *Cortbase* version 2.02 (see Parmasto *et al.* 2006), *Mycobank*, *CBS Aphyllophorales database*, and *Index Fungorum* were frequently consulted. Also Donk (1974), Ryvarden (1991) and several more recent taxonomic revisions for individual taxa were referred to when relevant. Generally, there was no attempt to include infraspecific taxa not widely recognized by taxonomists. These are listed under the section *Records with uncertain affinity*. Authors of fungal names are abbreviated as in www.indexfungorum.org/authorsoffungalnames.htm. Romanization of Russian authors' names (in citations) follows *Index Fungorum* or authors' own usage (e.g., Bondarzew instead of Bondartsev). Transliteration of Russian words follows the *BGN/PCGN* romanization system (see U.S. Board on Geographic Names 1994). The names of journals and periodicals appear as in *BPH-2* (Bridson 2004) where applicable. Herbaria acronyms are according to *Index Herbariorum* (www.nybg.org/bsci/ih/ih.html), and plant names agree with The International Plant Name Index, *IPNI* (www.ipni.org).

Checklist

In the following checklist, corticioid and polypore species are arranged in separate lists in alphabetic order. For each species, the accepted name in bold italic is listed first, followed by

its synonym(s) and names included in the taxon but not in current use, that were used in the literature treating the species in the studied area. Thereafter the supporting data appear: L signifies the literature, sorted by year of publication, and E stands for the examined specimens (selected unpublished material examined for this study). For literature data, a few potentially misleading misspellings are noted. Published records designated with sp., aff., cf. and ? are not included here, unless the respective material was re-examined. A few anamorphs are included which are in current use, excluding a direct reference to their teleomorph. Finally, the distribution (D) of the species in the Caucasus region is summarized by country abbreviation following Brummitt (2001): AR = Armenia, AZ = Azerbaijan, GR = Georgia, IRN = Iran, RUS = Russia, and TUR = Turkey (for the last three countries only Caucasian parts are meant here). *W Transcaucasus* is according to the distribution classes used by Davydina (1980), and we could not attribute it to the countries with certainty. Short notes are provided for some taxa. An asterisk (*) indicates new records for the Caucasus region, and a filled circle (•) records new to Iran. No attempt was made to indicate records new to other countries.

Corticioids

- **Aleurobotryus botryosus* (Burt) Boidin, Lanq. & Gilles – E—Georgia: Colchis, Poti, on *Rubus* sp., 30 Jul 1977, I. Parmasto (TAA 96956); on *Thuja* sp., 8 Aug 1977, Puusepp (TAA 109538). Iran: Gilan, Fuman, on dead twigs used in fences, 2 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 887. D—GR, IRN.
- Aleurocystidiellum disciforme* (Vill.) Boidin – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 233), Hallenberg & Parmasto (1998: 642), Larsson & Larsson (2003: 1039). D—RUS.
- Aleurodiscus amorphus* (Pers.) J. Schröt. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22613; Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12165. D—RUS.
- Aleurodiscus aurantius* (Pers.) J. Schröt. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Turkey: Trabzon, on twigs of *Rhododendron*, 27 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13278. D—RUS, TUR.
- Aleurodiscus cerussatus* (Bres.) Höhn. & Litsch. s. lat. – *Acanthophysellum cerussatum* (Bres.) Parmasto; *A. minor* (Pilát) Sheng H. Wu, Boidin & C.Y. Chien – L—Parmasto (1965b: 317), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 102); Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 272). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Amphinema byssoides* (Pers.) J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 233). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Pinus hamata*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 193110). Azerbaijan: Zakatali, Zakatali Nature Reserve, on *Quercus*, 6 Aug 1974, Murdvee (TAA 68345). Georgia: Adjara, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 7 Oct 1963,

- Parmasto (TAA 16791). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Pinus*, 16 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22568. D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Amyloathelia amylacea* (Bourdot & Galzin) Hjortstam & Ryvardeu – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Amylostereum areolatum* (Chaillat ex Fr.) Boidin – *Lloydella areolata* (Chaillat ex Fr.) Bres. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 183), Davydkina (1980: 83), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Sesli (2007: "14"). E—Turkey: Trabzon, on *Picea*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13271. D—RUS, TUR, W Transcaucasus.
- Amylostereum chailletii* (Pers.) Boidin – *Lloydella chailletii* (Pers.) Bres. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Davydkina (1980: 83), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 3 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16644). Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Abies*, 20 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13199. D—AZ, GR, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Amylostereum laevigatum* (Fr.) Boidin – L—Davydkina (1980: 85), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 273). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Taxus baccata*, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16270). Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on *Taxus*, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12967. D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Amyloxenasma allantosporum* (Oberw.) Hjortstam & Ryvardeu – *Xenasmatella allantospora* Oberw. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490). D—IRN.
- Amyloxenasma grisellum* (Bourdot) Hjortstam & Ryvardeu – *Xenasmatella grisella* (Bourdot) Oberw. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 491). E—Iran: E Azerbajjan, Kalibar, Tatar, 9 May 2008, Hallenberg 16178. D—IRN.
- **Aphanobasidium filicinum* (Bourdot) Jülich – E—Iran: Gilan, Fuman, Gasht-rud Khan, on twig on the ground, 2 May 2008, Hallenberg 16058. D—IRN. This species is known to grow on fern.
- **Aphanobasidium rubi* (Grosse-Brauckm.) Boidin & Gilles – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22590. D—RUS.
- **Aphanobasidium subnitens* (Bourdot & Galzin) Jülich – E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, alt. 1600 m, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11296. D—TUR.
- **Asterodon ferruginosus* Pat. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Abies*, 20 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13193. D—RUS.
- Asterostroma cervicolor* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Masee – *A. ochroleucum* Bres. – L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 132), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Asterostroma laxum* Bres. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Athelia arachnoidea* (Berk.) Jülich – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 285). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22509. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Athelia caucasica* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1968b: 199). E—Russia: Karachayevo-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 21 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 53186). D—GR, RUS.
- Athelia decipiens* (Höhn. & Litsch.) J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482, 1991: 357), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Zmitrovich (2008: 145). E—Iran: Gilan, Lahijan, 1 May 2008, Hallenberg 16028. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Athelia epiphylla* Pers. – *Hypochnus epiphyllus* (Pers.) Wallr. – L—Woronichin (1927: 151), Hallenberg (1981: 482), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234). E—Iran: Gilan, Asalem, 5 May 2008, Hallenberg 16113. Turkey: Trabzon, Çilekli, on *Picea*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11510. D—AZ, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Athelia rolfsii* (Curzi) C.C. Tu & Kimbr. – L—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR.
- Athelia salicum* Pers. – L—Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Zmitrovich (2008: 159). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 5 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16756). D—GR, RUS.
- Athelia tenuispora* Jülich – L—Zmitrovich (2008: 163). D—RUS.
- Athelia teutoburgensis* (Brinkmann) Jülich – *A. macrospora* var. *rhododendri* Parmasto; *Corticium teutoburgense* Brinkmann – L—Parmasto (1967: 382), Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Zmitrovich (2008: 163). D—GR, RUS.
- **Athelopsis lembospora* (Bourdot) Oberw. – E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on branch of hardwood tree, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11302. D—TUR.
- Basidioreadulum radula* (Fr.) Nobles – *Hyphoderma radula* (Fr.) Donk; *Radulum orbiculare* Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 109), Woronichin (1927: 153), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Nikolajeva (1961: 82), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Sesli (1999: 96), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: "5"). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on *Corylus*, 19 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13145. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- **Boidinia furfuracea* (Bres.) Stalpers & Hjortstam – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22532; Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Picea*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12064. D—RUS.
- Boreostereum radiatum* (Peck) Parmasto – *Stereum radiatum* Peck – L—Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 1992: 105, 2005: 236), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Botryobasidium aureum* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1964: 70, 1965a: 220, 1965b: 317), Eriksson & Ryvardeu (1973: 151), Hallenberg (1981: 482), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 9), Langer (1994: 68), Hjortstam & Ryvardeu (2007: 38). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22519. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Botryobasidium candicans* J. Erikss. – L—Parmasto (1965b: 317), Hallenberg (1981: 482), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Botryobasidium conspersum* J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Turkey:

- Trabzon, Maçka, on a trunk, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11341. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Botryobasidium curtisii* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Saber (1987: 28), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 10), Langer (1994: 122). E—Iran: Gilan, 32 km to Rasht from Rudbar, on hardwood trunk, 29 Apr 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 784. D—IRN.
- Botryobasidium grandinioides* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Langer (1994: 148). D—IRN.
- Botryobasidium laeve* (J. Erikss.) Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Langer (1994: 178). E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 3 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15319). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fagus*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22594. D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Botryobasidium medium* J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Botryobasidium obtusisporum* J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Langer (1994: 212). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on *Corylus*, 19 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13144. D—IRN, RUS.
- **Botryobasidium pruinatum* (Bres.) J. Erikss. – E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Platanus orientalis*, 2 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16278). D—AR.
- Botryobasidium robustior* Pouzar & Hol.-Jech. – L—Pouzar & Holubová-Jechova (1967: 69), Langer (1994: 250). D—AR.
- Botryobasidium subcoronatum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Armenia: Tavush, Noyemberyan, on *Quercus macranthera*, 14 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16102). Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Quercus castaneifolia*, 10 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15833). Iran: Gilan, Asalem, Gisum, 4 May 2008, Hallenberg 16101. Russia: Krasnodar, Labinsk, Voskresenovka, on trunks, 20 Jul 2000, Shiryaev (SVER 58033). Turkey: Trabzon, Çilekli, on *Fagus*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11508. D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Botryobasidium vagum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) D.P. Rogers – *B. botryosum* (Bres.) J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 482), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Langer (1994: 301). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22602; Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Pinus*, 13 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12263. D—IRN, RUS.
- Botryohypochnus isabellinus* (Fr.) J. Erikss. – *Botryobasidium isabellinum* (Fr.) D.P. Rogers; *Hypochnus flavus* (Bref.) Sacc. – L—Siemaszko (1923: 27), Parmasto (1968c: 406), Hallenberg (1981: 482), Langer (1994: 168). E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 3 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15312). Azerbaijan: Khachmaz, Khachmaz, on *Quercus longipes*, 29 Oct 1981, Parmasto (TAA 104135). Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 7 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16819). Turkey: Trabzon, Çilekli, on *Picea*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11517. D—The whole area.
- Brevicellicium olivascens* (Bres.) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – *Grandinia mutabilis* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin; *Trechispora mutabilis* (Pers.) Liberta – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 74), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 104), Hallenberg (1981: 482, 1991: 358). D—AZ, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Bulbillomyces farinosus* (Bres.) Jülich – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Georgia: Colchis, Poti, on a fallen twig, 11 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16855). Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11584 (as *Aegerita candida* Pers.). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Byssocorticium atrovirens* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Parmasto (1966: 372), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Zmitrovich (2008: 171). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Castanea sativa*, 17 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16921). Turkey: Trabzon, Sumela monastery, on wood, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11590. D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- **Byssocorticium pulchrum* (S. Lundell) M.P. Christ. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Psebay, on *Acer*, 6 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 11993. D—RUS.
- Byssomerulius albostramineus* (Torrend) Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Zmitrovich (2008: 216). D—RUS.
- Byssomerulius corium* (Pers.) Parmasto – *Meruliopsis corium* (Pers.) Ginns; *Merulius corium* (Pers.) Fr.; *Stereum ochroleucum* (Fr.) Quél. – L—Bondarzew (1912: 118), Woronow (1915: 106, 112), Woronichin (1916: 16, 1927: 152, 154), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Parmasto (1968a: 41), Saber (1974: 21), Hallenberg (1981: 482), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Melia *et al.* (1987: 93, 116, 161, 180, 191), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Byssomerulius hirtellus* (Burt) Parmasto – *B. armeniacus* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1967: 383, 1968a: 41). D—AR.
- Candelabrochaete septocystidia* (Burt) Burds. – *Phanerochaete septocystidia* (Burt) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487). E—Iran: Gilan, Siahkal, on *Fagus*, 30 Apr 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 816. D—IRN.
- Ceraceomyces borealis* (Romell) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 483), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Zmitrovich (2008: 122). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12060. D—IRN, RUS.
- Ceraceomyces serpens* (Tode) Ginns – *Ceraceomerulius serpens* (Fr.) Ginns; *Merulius serpens* (Tode) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 112), Hallenberg (1981: 483), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 286). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Ceraceomyces tessulatus* (Cooke) Jülich – *Athelia tessulata* (Cooke) Donk – L—Parmasto (1966: 372), Zmitrovich (2008: 110). D—GR, RUS.
- Chaetodermella luna* (Romell ex D.P. Rogers & H.S. Jacks.) Rauschert – *Chaetoderma luna* (Romell ex D.P. Rogers & H.S. Jacks.) Parmasto – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234). D—RUS.

- Chondrostereum purpureum* (Pers.) Pouzar – *Stereum purpureum* Pers. – L—Woronichin (1915a: 14, 1915b: 114, 1927: 152), Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Khabiri (1968: 137), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 328), Saber (1974: 21), Davydkina (1980: 95), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 483, 1991: 358), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Sesli (1999: 96), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Nikolayev (2001: 99), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 478), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Clavulicium macounii* (Burt) J. Erikss. & Boidin ex Parmasto – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 12 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12240. D—RUS.
- Conferticium ochraceum* (Fr.) Hallenb. – *C. insidiosum* (Bourdot & Galzin) Hallenb.; *Corticium ochraceum* (Fr.) Fr. – L—Rabenhorst (1871: 23), Woronow (1915: 103), Hallenberg (1981: 483). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1400 m, on a log of *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12088. D—IRN, RUS.
- Coniophora arida* (Fr.) P. Karst. – L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 153). E—Georgia: Colchis, Poti, on *Alnus barbata*, 11 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16860). Russia: Krasnodar, on *Pyrus caucasica*, 29 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 19798). D—GR, RUS. Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986) enumerate it from Transcaucasus.
- Coniophora olivacea* (Fr.) P. Karst. – *Coniophorella olivacea* (Fr.) P. Karst. – L—Woronow (1915: 105), Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 430), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Coniophora puteana* (Schumach.) P. Karst. – *C. cerebella* Alb. & Schwein.; *C. membranacea* DC. – L—Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 78), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 491), Simonyan (1981: 150), Arzumanyan (1982: 44, 1986: 16), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 91), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 405), Nikolayev (2001: 99), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 463). E—Iran: Gilan, Rezvanshahr, 4 May 2008, Hallenberg 16091. Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22645. D—The whole area.
- **Corticium erikssonii* Jülich – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22542. D—RUS.
- Corticium roseum* Pers. – *Laeticorticium roseum* (Pers.) Donk – L—Woronichin (1927: 151), Singer (1931: 516), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 287). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Populus alba*, 12 Oct 1962, Parmasto, (TAA 15812). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- **Cotylidia pannosa* (Sowerby) D.A. Reid – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, alt. 1600–1700 m, on soil, 16 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 18735). D—RUS.
- Cristinia eichleri* (Bres.) Nakasone – *C. gallica* (Pilát) Jülich; *Hydnum mucidum* Pers. – L—Woronow (1915: 110, 1927: 154), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Umpyr', on *Pinus* sp., 11 Aug 1976, Puusepp (TAA 109110); Adygeya, Maykop, on *Abies*, 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22646. D—GR, RUS.
- Cristinia helvetica* (Pers.) Parmasto – *Grandinia helvetica* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 69), Hallenberg (1981: 483). E—Armenia: Noyemberyan, on dead leaves of *Carpinus caucasica*, 15 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16178). Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Fagus*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12097. D—AR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Crustoderma dryinum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Parmasto – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12180. D—RUS.
- Crustomyces expallens* (Bres.) Hjortstam – *Cystostereum stratosum* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 483), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 18). D—IRN.
- Crustomyces heteromorphus* (Hallenb.) Hjortstam – *Cystostereum heteromorphum* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 483). D—IRN.
- Crustomyces subabruptus* (Bourdot & Galzin) Jülich – *Cystostereum pini-canadense* subsp. *subabruptum* (Bourdot & Galzin) Chamuris; *C. subabruptum* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. & Ryvarde; *Odontia subabrupta* Bourdot & Galzin – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 103), Hallenberg (1981: 483), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Noyemberyan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 14 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15390). Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Fagus orientalis*, 18 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16225). Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on *Taxus cuspidata*, Oct 1966, Vasil'eva (TAA 195405). Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11295. D—The whole area.
- **Cylindrobasidium eucalypti* (M. Dueñas & Tellería) Tellería & Melo – E—Iran: Gilan, Fuman, on *Pterocarya fraxinifolia*, 2 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 870. D—IRN.
- Cylindrobasidium evolvens* (Fr.) Jülich – *Corticium evolvens* (Fr.) Fr.; *C. laeve* Pers.; *Cylindrobasidium laeve* (Pers.) Chamuris – L—Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 483), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Melia *et al.* (1987: 81), Hallenberg (1991: 359). E—Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Tilia platyphyllos*, 12 Aug 1974, Puusepp (TAA 90801). Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Rubus* sp., 5 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16773). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Salix*, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22537. D—The whole area.

- **Cylindrobasidium torrendii* (Bres.) Hjortstam – E—Iran: Gilan, Fuman, Qale-rud Khan, on a branch of *Sambucus*, 2 May 2008, Hallenberg 16049; Masal, on a fallen branch, 3 May, Hallenberg 16066. D—IRN.
- Cystostereum murrayi* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Pouzar – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Davydkina (1980: 97), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22511. D—AZ, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Dacryobolus karstenii* (Bres.) Oberw. ex Parmasto – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12114. D—RUS.
- Dacryobolus sudans* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. – *Odontia sudans* (Alb. & Schwein.) Bres. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 105), Hallenberg (1981: 483, 1991: 359), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234). D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Dendrocorticium polygonioides* (P. Karst.) M.J. Larsen & Gilb. – L—Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 274). D—IRN.
- Dendrophora albobadia* (Schwein.) Chamuris – *Lopharia heterospora* (Burt) D.A. Reid – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485). D—IRN.
- Dendrophora versiformis* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Chamuris – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22592. Turkey: Trabzon, S of Tonya, on *Alnus* litter, 8 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11444. D—RUS, TUR.
- Dendrothele acerina* (Pers.) P.A. Lemke – *Vuilleminia acerina* (Pers.) Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 483), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Kummer (2007: 155, 202). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Acer velutinum*, 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15943). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Acer*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22605. D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Dendrothele alliacea* (Quél.) P.A. Lemke – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Dendrothele commixta* (Höhn. & Litsch.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Dendrothele griseocana* (Bres.) Bourdot & Galzin – *Dendrothele papillosa* Höhn. & Litsch. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Dendrothele incrustans* (P.A. Lemke) P.A. Lemke – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- **Dichostereum effuscatum* (Cooke & Ellis) Boidin & Lanq. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Fagus*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12049. D—RUS.
- Dichostereum granulorum* (Pers.) Boidin & Lanq. – *Grandinia granulosa* (Pers.) P. Karst.; *Vararia granulosa* (Pers.) Laurila – L—Parmasto (1970: 85), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22650a. D—GR, RUS.
- Erythricium salmonicolor* (Berk. & Broome) Burds. – *Corticium javanicum* (Henn.) Sacc. & P. Syd. – L—Speshnev (1902: 72, 1904: 90), Mordue & Gibson (1976: descr. no. 511). D—GR, RUS.
- Fibricium subceraceum* (Hallenb.) Bernicchia – *Fibrodonia subceracea* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 483), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 24). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13029. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on hardwood branch, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11547. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Fibrodonia gossypina* Parmasto – *Hyphodontia gossypina* (Parmasto) Hjortstam – L—Parmasto (1968b: 207), Hallenberg (1981: 483), Langer (1994: 118). D—The whole area.
- Flavophlebia sulfureoisabellina* (Litsch.) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – L—Hjortstam & Larsson (1977: 475), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—GR, RUS.
- Galzinia incrustans* Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—IRN, RUS.
- Galzinia longibasidia* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484). D—IRN.
- Gloeocystidiellum citrinellum* E. Larss. & K.H. Larss. – L—Larsson & Larsson (“2002”: 3). D—RUS.
- **Gloeocystidiellum clavuligerum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Nakasone – L—Hallenberg (1991: 361), Larsson & Hallenberg (2001: 909), Larsson & Larsson (“2002”: 3, 2003: 1040). E—Iran: Gilan, Masal, Dasht-gid, on CWD of a deciduous tree, 3 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 911. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Gloeocystidiellum permixtum* (Boidin, Lanq. & Gilles) E. Larss. & K.H. Larss. – L—Larsson & Larsson (“2002”: 3). D—TUR.
- Gloeocystidiellum porosum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484, 1991: 362), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Larsson & Hallenberg (2001: 909), Larsson & Larsson (“2002”: 3). D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Gloeodontia columbiensis* Burt ex Burds. & Lombard – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484, 1991: 362). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Prunus armeniaca*, 28 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15460). D—AR, IRN, TUR.
- Gloiothele lactescens* (Berk.) Hjortstam – *Gloeocystidiellum lactescens* (Berk.) Boidin – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484). E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Ulmus scabra*, 3 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15324). Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Acer velutinum*, 10 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15835). Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Psebay, on decayed deciduous wood, 14 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12294. D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Haplotrichum capitatum* (Link) Willd. – *Oidium candicans* (Sacc.) Linder – L—Parmasto (1964: 71, 1965b: 317, 318, 1968d: 90), Holubová-Jechova (1980: 141). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Haplotrichum conspersum* (Link) Hol.-Jech. – *Oidium conspersum* (Fr.) Linder – L—Parmasto (1964: 71, 1968d: 89), Saber (1987: 28). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Haplotrichum curtisii* (Berk.) Hol.-Jech. – *Oidium curtisii* (Berk.) Linder – L—Parmasto (1964: 70, 1965b: 318, 1968d: 91), Saber (1987: 28, 2002: 286), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74). D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS.

- Haplotrichum dubium* (Pers.) Baker & Partridge – *H. aureum* (Pers.) Hol.-Jech.; *Oidium aureum* Fr. – L—Parmasto (1964: 70, 1968d: 88), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Haplotrichum rubiginosum* (Fr.) Hol.-Jech. – *Oidium rubiginosum* (Fr.) Linder – L—Parmasto (1964: 71, 1965b: 318, 1968d: 91). D—AR, RUS.
- Hydnocristella himantia* (Schwein.) R.H. Petersen – *Hydnum himantia* Schwein.; *Kavinia himantia* (Schwein.) J. Erikss. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on forest litter, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15518). Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Sambucus* sp., 12 Aug 1974, Parmasto (TAA 68427). Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on *Buxus*, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12957. D—AR, AZ, RUS.
- **Hydnomerulius pinastri* (Fr.) Jarosch & Besl. – *Leucogyrophana pinastri* (Fr.) Ginns & Weresub – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12116. D—RUS.
- Hymenochaete carpatica* Pilát – L—Kummer (2007: 155, 202). D—RUS.
- Hymenochaete cinnamomea* (Pers.) Bres. – L—Woronow (1915: 105), Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 29), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). E—Armenia: Tavush, Kirovakan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 19 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15146). Azerbaijan: Astara, Lenkoran', on *Alnus barbata*, 21 May 1977, Parmasto (52984 TAA). Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on branch of a hardwood tree, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11283. D—The whole area.
- Hymenochaete corrugata* (Fr.) Lév. – L—Woronow (1915: 105), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 103), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Hymenochaete cruenta* (Pers.) Donk – *H. mougeotii* (Fr.) Cooke – L—Woronow (1923: 184), Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 35), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 13), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 148, 202). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22600. D—GR, RUS.
- Hymenochaete fuliginosa* (Pers.) Lév. – L—Woronow (1915: 106), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 33), Kummer (2007: 148, 202). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12168. D—GR, RUS.
- Hymenochaete minuscula* G. Cunn. – *H. caucasica* Parmasto – L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 29), Parmasto (1986: 374), Léger (1998: 86). D—GR.
- Hymenochaete rubiginosa* (Dicks.) Lév. – *H. ferruginea* (Bull.) Bres.; *Stereum ferrugineum* (Bull.) Fr.; *S. rubiginosum* (Dicks.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 316), Filarszky (1907: 15), Woronow (1915: 106), Woronichin (1927: 152), Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 37), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 135, 148, 176), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Léger (1998: 245), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 180), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Quercus iberica*, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15165). Azerbaijan: Astara, Lenkoran', on *Quercus castaneifolia*, 19 May 1977, Parmasto (TAA 100660). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Darana, 10 May 2008, Hallenberg 16211. D—The whole area.
- Hymenochaete subfuliginosa* Bourdot & Galzin – L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 38). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Hymenochaete tabacina* (Sowerby) Lév. – *H. crocata* (Fr.) Lév. – L—Woronow (1915: 106), Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Hyphoderma argillaceum* (Bres.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Fagus orientalis*, 9 Aug 1974, Puusepp (TAA 90622). Georgia: Colchis, Chakva, on *Pinus taeda*, 28 Sep 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16048). Iran: Gilan, Rezvanshahr, 4 May 2008, Hallenberg 16090. Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22536. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11559. D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphoderma cremeoalbum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Jülich – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484, 1991: 363). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Khoda-afarin, Darana, on fallen branch of a deciduous tree, 10 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1138. Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1400 m, on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12098. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphoderma definitum* (H.S. Jacks.) Donk – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Nilsson *et al.* (2003: 467), Paulus *et al.* (2007: 142). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11561. D—RUS, TUR.
- Hyphoderma litschaueri* (Burt) J. Erikss. & Å. Strid – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 275). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Alnus barbata*, 19 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 15248). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- **Hyphoderma macedonicum* (Litsch.) Donk – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Umpyr', on *Fagus orientalis*, 12 Aug 1976, Puusepp (TAA 109137); Krasnodar, Adler, on *Acer*, 21 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13226. Turkey: Trabzon, Uçarsu, on hardwood branch, 9 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11490. D—RUS, TUR.
- **Hyphoderma malenconii* (Manjón & G. Moreno) Manjón, G. Moreno & Hjortstam – E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 26 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15521). D—AR.

- Hyphoderma medioburiense* (Burt) Donk – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Hyphoderma mutatum* (Peck) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Armenia: Noyemberyan, on hardwood bark, 14 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16192). Russia: Krasnodar, Novorossiysk, on deciduous wood, 6 Aug 2000, Shiryayev (SVR 58036). D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Hyphoderma nemorale* K.H. Larss. – L—Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 287). E—Russia: Karachayevo-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 17 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 011). D—IRN, RUS.
- Hyphoderma occidentale* (D.P. Rogers) Boidin & Gilles – *H. subdefinitum* J. Erikss. & Å. Strid – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- **Hyphoderma orphanellum* (Bourdout & Galzin) Donk – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Alnus*, 12 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12208. D—RUS.
- Hyphoderma roseocremeum* (Bres.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484, 1991: 364), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16219. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphoderma setigerum* (Fr.) Donk – *Odontia setigera* (Fr.) L.W. Mill.; *Peniophora setigera* (Fr.) Höhn. & Litsch. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Nikolajeva (1961: 107), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 484), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234), Nilsson *et al.* (2003: 467), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Darana, 10 May 2008, Hallenberg 16201. Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fagus*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22585. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Hyphoderma sibiricum* (Parmasto) J. Erikss. & Å. Strid – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Hyphoderma transiens* (Bres.) Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485, 1991: 364). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Quercus castaneifolia*, 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15929). Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 17 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 15259). Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Naharkhoran, on *Carpinus*, 29 Oct 2007, Ghobad-Nejhad 650. Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Psebay, on a branch of a deciduous tree, 15 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12304. D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodermella corrugata* (Fr.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Dasiphora fruticosa*, 28 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15491). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Vaighan, on *Quercus*, 2 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 402. Turkey: Trabzon, S of Tonya, on *Alnus* litter, 8 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11447. D—AR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia alutacea* (Fr.) J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Hyphodontia abieticola* (Bourdout & Galzin) J. Erikss. – L—Langer (1994: 24). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12100. D—RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia alienata* (S. Lundell) J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on decayed wood, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13034. D—RUS.
- **Hyphodontia alutaria* (Burt) J. Erikss. – *Odontia alutaria* (Burt) Nikol. – L—Nikolajeva (1964: 168). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jolfa, Daran, on *Ulmus glabra*, 25 Apr 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 753. Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12106. Turkey: Trabzon, Çilekli, on *Picea*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11511. D—AR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia arguta* (Fr.) J. Erikss. – *Grandinia arguta* (Fr.) Jülich; *Odontia arguta* (Fr.) Quél.; *O. stipata* (Fr.) Quél. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 112, 118), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 55), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Noyemberyan, on *Sambucus nigra*, 15 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15685). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Hyphodontia aspera* (Fr.) J. Erikss. – *Odontia aspera* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 116), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Fagus*, 16 Sep 1962, Raitviir (TAA 43036). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Hyphodontia barba-jovis* (Bull.) J. Erikss. – *Kneiffiella barba-jovis* (Bull.) P. Karst.; *Odontia barba-jovis* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 110), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15547). Turkey: Rize, S of Çamlıhemşin, on *Alnus*, 5 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11403. D—AR, RUS, TUR.
- **Hyphodontia borealis* Kotir. & Saaren. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Matteuccia*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13252. D—RUS.
- Hyphodontia breviseta* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 72). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Castanea sativa*, 19 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 15241). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia bugellensis* (Ces.) J. Erikss. – *Odontia bugellensis* Ces. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 130). D—W Transcaucasus.
- Hyphodontia crustosa* (Pers.) J. Erikss. – *Odontia albicans* (Pers.) L.W. Mill. & J.S. Boyle; *O. crustosa* Pers. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 123, 130), Parmasto (1968a: 41), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 87). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 16 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15339). Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Crataegus* sp., 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (15952 TAA). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Qale-darasi, on hardwood branch, 5 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 461. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- **Hyphodontia curvispora* J. Erikss. & Hjortstam – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12095. D—RUS.

- Hyphodontia erastii* Saaren. & Kotir. – L—Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 276). D—IRN.
- Hyphodontia flavipora* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis ex Cooke) Sheng H. Wu – *Poria confusa* Bres.; *Schizopora carneolutea* (Rodway & Cleland) Kotl. & Pouzar; *S. flavipora* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis ex Cooke) Ryvarden; *S. paradoxa* var. *microporus* (Komarova) – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 443), Saber (1987: 25, 2000: 374), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Hallenberg (1991: 374), Langer (1994: 106), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: Gilan, Lahijan, on dead decorticated wood, 1 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 843. D—GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia floccosa* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. – *Odontia floccosa* (Bourdot & Galzin) Nikol. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 126). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Pinus*, 13 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12249. D—RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Hyphodontia halonata* J. Erikss. & Hjortstam – L—Langer (1994: 125). D—RUS.
- Hyphodontia juniperi* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. & Hjortstam – L—Eriksson *et al.* (1981: 1067), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Langer (1994: 137). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on *Buxus*, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12962. D—IRN, RUS.
- Hyphodontia nespori* (Bres.) J. Erikss. & Hjortstam – *Grandinia nespori* (Bres.) Cejp – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485, 1991: 365), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 158), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia pallidula* (Bres.) J. Erikss. – L—Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 3 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16661). Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on log of a broad-leaved tree, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12968. Turkey: Trabzon, on a stump of *Picea*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13264. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- *Hyphodontia paradoxa* (Schrad.) E. Langer & Vesterh. – *Irpex deformis* Fr.; *I. obliquus* (Schrad.) Fr.; *I. paradoxus* (Schrad.) Fr.; *Schizopora paradoxa* (Schrad.) Donk [incl. f. *irpex paradoxus* (Schrad.) Bourdot & Galzin]; *Xylodon versiporus* (Pers.) Bondartsev – L—Woronichin (1915a: 14, 1927: 154), Woronow (1915: 111), Singer (1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Bondarzew (1953: 128), Kanygina (1964: 38), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 171), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 443), Melia *et al.* (1987: 89, 122), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89), Bondartseva (1998: 303), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Parrotia persica*, 14 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15849). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Darana, on a fallen branch, 10 May 2008, Hallenberg 16209; Kaleibar, Kalaleh, on *Carpinus*, 11 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1221. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Hyphodontia pruni* (Lasch) Svrček – *Odontia pruni* Lasch – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 133), Popushoy (1971: 200), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 103), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 192). D—GR, RUS, TUR, W Transcaucasus.
- Hyphodontia quercina* (Pers.) J. Erikss. [incl. *H. quercina* f. *coralloides* Hallenb.] – *Grandinia quercina* (Pers.) Jülich; *Odontia fallax* (Fr.) Quél.; *Radulum fagineum* (Pers.) Fr.; *R. quercinum* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 109), Nikolajeva (1961: 90), Hallenberg (1981: 485, 1991: 365), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Melia *et al.* (1987: 472), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234), Langer (1994: 197), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15515). D—The whole area.
- Hyphodontia radula* (Pers.) Langer & Vesterh. – *Chaetoporus radula* (Pers.) Bondartsev & Singer; *C. varicolor* (P. Karst.) Parmasto; *Poria radula* Pers.; *Schizopora radula* (Pers.) Hallenb.; *Xylodon versiporus* var. *radula* (Bourdot & Galzin) Domański – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Kanygina (1964: 38), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 185), Hallenberg (1981: 495 as *S. paradoxa*, 1991: 375), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429, 445), Saber (1987: 25), Langer (1994: 182 as *S. paradoxa*, 200), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403, 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Apsheronk, Pyatigorsk, on *Quercus petraea*, 1 Oct 1966, Parmasto (19826 TAA). D—The whole area.
- Hyphodontia rimosissima* (Peck) Gilb. – *H. papillosa* (Fr.) J. Erikss.; *Odontia papillosa* (Fr.) Bres. – L—Woronow (1915: 109), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Nikolajeva (1961: 124), Parmasto (1968a: 42), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Melia *et al.* (1987: 423). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Alnus*, 21 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13246. D—AZ, GR, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Hyphodontia sambuci* (Pers.) J. Erikss. – *Corticium serum* (Pers.) Fr.; *Hyphoderma sambuci* (Pers.) Jülich – L—Woronow (1915: 103), Hallenberg (1981: 484), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 422, 469), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 206), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Platanus digitatifolia*, 2 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16385). Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Sambucus ebulus*, 8 Aug 1974, Puusepp (TAA 90604). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Sambucus* sp., 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22635. Turkey: Trabzon, S of Tonya, on *Alnus* litter, 8 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11448. D—The whole area.
- Hyphodontia spathulata* (Schrad.) Parmasto – *Odontia arguta* f. *spathulata* (Fr.) Wakfield. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 114), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on a trunk, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11344. D—AZ, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hyphodontia subalutacea* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485, 1991: 366), Mukhamedshin

- (1992: 106), Langer (1994: 220), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 287). D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hypochniciellum ovoideum* (Jülich) Hjortstam & Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485). D—IRN.
- Hypochnicium analogum* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. – *Gloeocystidium analogum* Bourdot & Galzin; *Gloeohypochnicium analogum* (Bourdot & Galzin) Hjortstam – L—Woronow (1915: 105), Eriksson & Ryvarden (1976: 694), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 12), Larsson & Larsson (2003: 1040), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 986), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Hypochnicium bombycinum* (Sommerf.) J. Erikss. – *Radulum bombycinum* (Sommerf.) Nikol. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 86), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Parrotia persica*, 10 Oct 1962, Parmaso (TAA 16428). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Hypochnicium cymosum* (D.P. Rogers & H.S. Jacks.) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Hypochnicium erikssonii* Hallenb. & Hjortstam – *H. sphaerosporum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12174. Turkey: Rize, S of Çamlıhemşin, on a branch, 5 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11440. D—RUS, TUR.
- **Hypochnicium geogenium* (Bres.) J. Erikss. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12197. D—RUS.
- **Hypochnicium karstenii* (Bres.) Hallenb. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22545. D—RUS.
- Hypochnicium lundellii* (Bourdot) J. Erikss. – L—Eriksson & Ryvarden (1976: 713), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 18 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16232). D—GR, RUS.
- Hypochnicium polonense* (Bres.) Å. Strid – L—Hallenberg (1981: 485, 1991: 368), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Paulus *et al.* (2007: 141). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15571). Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Fagus orientalis*, 18 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16233). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Hypochnicium punctulatum* (Cooke) J. Erikss. – *H. eichleri* (Bres.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Vakfikebir, on *Fagus*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11531; Trabzon, Sumela monastery, on *Fagus*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11338. D—RUS, TUR.
- **Hypochnicium subrigescens* Boidin – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13043. D—RUS.
- Hypochnicium vellereum* (Ellis & Cragin) Parmasto – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Fraxinus excelsior*, 26 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15434). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on deciduous wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22535. D—AR, RUS.
- Hypochnicium wakefieldiae* (Bres.) J. Erikss. – *H. caucasicum* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1967: 385, 1968a: 42), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 35), Nilsson & Hallenberg (2003: 56), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Hjortstam & Ryvarden (2007: 78), Paulus *et al.* (2007: 141). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Intextomyces contiguus* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – *Corticium crustaceum* (P. Karst.) Höhn. & Litsch. – L—Khabiri (1968: 137). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Laurocerasus officinalis*, 17 Oct 1963 Parmasto (TAA 15211). Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Guzerip', on *Pyrus caucasica*, 20 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 19654). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- **Intextomyces cystidiatus* Hjortstam – E—Russia: Karachayevo-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on hardwood, 25 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 53307). D—RUS.
- Irpicodon pendulus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Pouzar – *Irpex pendulus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr.; *Radulum pendulinum* Nikol. – L—Woronow (1915: 111), Nikolajeva (1961: 95), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436, 442), Bondartseva (1998: 65), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Jaapia argillacea* Bres. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Alnus*, 12 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12209. D—RUS.
- **Jaapia ochroleuca* (Bres.) Nannf. & J. Erikss. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Acer*, 21 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13232; Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12096. D—RUS.
- Lagarobasidium detriticum* (Bourdot) Jülich – *Hyphodontia detritica* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss.; *Hypochnicium detriticum* (Bourdot) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Eriksson & Ryvarden (1976: 703), Langer (1994: 96). D—GR, TUR.
- Laxitextum bicolor* (Pers.) Lentz – *Lloydella fusca* (Schrad.) Bres. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Davydkina (1980: 99), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Larsson & Hallenberg (2001: 909), Larsson & Larsson ("2002": 3). E—Armenia: Noyemberyan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 13 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15381). Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Fagus orientalis*, 18 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16228). Iran: Ardabil, Andabil, on hardwood branch, 6 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1020. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Leptosporomyces fuscostratus* (Burt) Hjortstam – L—Zmitrovich (2008: 176). D—RUS.
- **Leptosporomyces galzinii* (Bourdot) Jülich – E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Pinus hamata*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15530). Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 3 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16031). Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Abies*, 20 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13207; Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on deciduous wood, 7 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12036. D—AR, GR, RUS.

- **Leptosporomyces mutabilis* (Bres.) Krieglst. — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Pinus*, 16 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22567. D—RUS.
- Leptosporomyces septentrionalis* (J. Erikss.) Krieglst. — *Fibulomyces septentrionalis* (J. Erikss.) Jülich — L—Hallenberg (1981: 484). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Fagus*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12057. D—IRN, RUS.
- Leucogyrophana mollusca* (Fr.) Pouzar — L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 162), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Leucogyrophana pulverulenta* (Sowerby) Ginns — *Serpula minor* (Falck) Bondartsev; *S. tignicola* (Harmsen) M.P. Christ. — L—Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Ivanova (1985: 89). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- **Lindtneria leucobryophila* (Henn.) Jülich — E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, Getashen, on *Fagus orientalis*, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15502). D—AR.
- **Litschauerella clematitidis* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. & Ryvarde — E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea* trunk, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11359. D—TUR.
- **Lobulicium occultum* K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22533. D—RUS.
- Lopharia cinerascens* (Schwein.) G. Cunn. — *Lloydella cinerascens* (Schwein.) Bres. — L—Woronow (1915: 106). D—GR.
- **Luellia recondita* (H.S. Jacks.) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam — E—Georgia: Colchis, Chakva, on *Cryptomeria japonica*, 28 Sep 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16992). D—GR.
- Megalocystidium leucoxanthum* (Bres.) Jülich — *Gloeocystidiellum leucoxanthum* (Bres.) Boidin — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22591. D—RUS.
- Megalocystidium luridum* (Bres.) Jülich — *Gloeocystidiellum luridum* (Bres.) Boidin — L—Parmasto (1965b: 318), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 277). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Acer* sp., 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22644. D—AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Melzericium bourdotii* Jülich — L—Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 279). D—IRN.
- **Membranomyces delectabilis* (H.S. Jacks.) Kotir. & Saaren. — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Guzeripl', on *Abies nordmanniana*, 19 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 19598); Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Pinus*, 7 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12014. D—RUS.
- **Membranomyces spurius* (Bourdot) Jülich — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, S of Mt. Kolokol'naya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 19 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13157. D—RUS.
- Metulodontia nivea* (P. Karst.) Parmasto — *Athelia sublaevis* (Bres.) Parmasto; *Ceraceomyces sublaevis* (Bres.) Jülich; *Corticium sublaeve* Bres. — L—Parmasto (1974: 42), Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Larsson & Larsson (2003: 1041), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on hardwood stump, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11394. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora aurantiaca* (Bres.) Höhn. & Litsch. — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Sesli (1999: 96), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 464). D—RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora cinerea* (Pers.) Cooke — *Kneiffia cinerea* (Pers.) Bres. — L—Woronow (1915: 101, 104, 109), Nagorny (1930: 61), Hallenberg (1981: 486), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 236, 360, 362, 423, 437), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89), Hallenberg & Larsson (1992: 1759), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fraxinus excelsior*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22505. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora erikssonii* Boidin — L—Eriksson *et al.* (1978: 925), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Peniophora incarnata* (Pers.) P. Karst. — *Gloeopeniophora incarnata* (Pers.) Höhn. & Litsch. — L—Woronow (1915: 105), Vasil'eva (1939: 34), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Saber (1974: 20), Hallenberg (1981: 486, 1991: 369), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 102, 398), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora junipericola* J. Erikss. — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Peniophora laeta* (Fr.) Donk — L—Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 281). D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora laurentii* S. Lundell — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Peniophora lilacea* Bourdot & Galzin — L—Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 486), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16228. D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Peniophora limitata* (Chaillat ex Fr.) Cooke — L—Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181). E—Armenia: Tavush, Kirovakan, on *Fraxinus excelsior*, 19 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15178). Azerbaijan: Khachmaz, Kusarski, on *Fraxinus excelsior*, 13 May 1983, Parmasto (TAA 105250). D—AR, AZ, RUS.
- Peniophora lycii* (Pers.) Höhn. & Litsch. — *Peniophora caesia* Bres. — L—Woronow (1915: 104), Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 486, 1991: 369), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 236, 458), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 405), Saber (2002: 286), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Peniophora meridionalis* Boidin — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Peniophora nuda* (Fr.) Bres. — L—Woronow (1915: 104), Hallenberg (1981: 486, 1986: 74, 1991: 370),

- Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 94), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 288). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora piceae* (Pers.) J. Erikss. – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22579. D—RUS.
- **Peniophora pilatiana* Pouzar & Svrček – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of *Pterocarya*, 19 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13168. D—RUS.
- Peniophora pini* (Schleich. & DC.) Boidin – *Stereum pini* (Schleich. & DC.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 316), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 107), Woronichin (1927: 152), Davydkina (1980: 101), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Melia *et al.* (1987: 33), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181), Hallenberg & Parmasto (1998: 642), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Pinus hamata*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16259). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Peniophora pithya* (Pers.) J. Erikss. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 7 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16794). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora polygonia* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin – *Aleurodiscus polygonius* (Pers.) Höhn. & Litsch. – L—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 88, 1999: 128), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Georgia: Colchis, Poti, on *Populus* sp., 12 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16878). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Peniophora proxima* Bres. – L—Woronow (1915: 104), Parmasto (1966: 373), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 486), Melia *et al.* (1987: 400). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on log of *Buxus*, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12955. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Peniophora pseudonuda* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 486, 1991: 370), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Corylus avellana*, 5 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16745). Iran: Gilan, Lahijan, 1 May 2008, Hallenberg 16031. Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fagus orientalis*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22517. Turkey: Trabzon, on *Fagus*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13253. D—GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- **Peniophora pseudoversicolor* Boidin – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487 as *Peniophora* sp.). D—IRN.
- Peniophora quercina* (Pers.) Cooke [incl. *P. quercina* f. *phlebioides* Hallenb. and subsp. *caucasica* Parmasto & I. Parmasto] – *Kneiffia corticalis* (Bull.) Bres.; *Peniophora corticalis* (Bull.) Bres. – L—Woronichin (1915b: 114), Woronow (1915: 104), Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 486), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 94, 106, 155, 307), Parmasto & Parmasto (1987: 139, 1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Turkey: Trabzon, on *Quercus*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13273. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophora rufa* (Fr.) Boidin – *Hymenochaete rufa* (Fr.) Jacz. – L—Woronow (1915: 106), Davydkina (1980: 102), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1996: 181), Hallenberg & Parmasto (1998: 642). D—RUS.
- Peniophora rufomarginata* (Pers.) Litsch. – L—Woronow (1915: 104 as *P. corticalis*; also Melia *et al.* 1987: 458), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS
- Peniophora septentrionalis* Laurila – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Peniophora violaceolivida* (Sommerf.) Masee – L—Woronow (1915: 105), Hallenberg (1981: 487), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 289). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Peniophorella echinocystis* (J. Erikss. & Å. Strid) K.H. Larss. – *Hyphoderma echinocystis* J. Erikss. & Å. Strid – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484). D—IRN.
- Peniophorella guttulifera* (P. Karst.) K.H. Larss. – *Hyphoderma guttuliferum* (P. Karst.) Donk – L—Larsson *et al.* (2004: 987), Hallenberg *et al.* (2007: 1371). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Fagus orientalis*, 18 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 15154). D—GR, RUS.
- Peniophorella pallida* (Bres.) K.H. Larss. – *Hyphoderma pallidum* (Bres.) Donk; *H. tsugae* (Burt) J. Erikss. & Å. Strid – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 3 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16030). Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11291. D—GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophorella pertenuis* (P. Karst.) Hallenb. & R.H. Nilsson – L—Hallenberg *et al.* (2007: 1370). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22540. D—RUS, TUR.
- Peniophorella praetermissa* (P. Karst.) K.H. Larss. s. lat. – *Hyphoderma praetermissum* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. & Å. Strid – L—Hallenberg (1981: 484), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Hallenberg *et al.* (1994: 1013), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Hallenberg *et al.* (2007: 1371). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Quercus macranthera*, 17 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15627). Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on hardwood, 5 Aug 1974, Kullman (TAA 68005). Georgia: Colchis, Poti, on *Populus* sp., 7 Aug 1977, Puusepp (TAA 109503). D—AZ, IRN, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Peniophorella praetermissa* (P. Karst.) K.H. Larss. s. str. – L—Hallenberg *et al.* (2007: 1370). D—RUS, TUR.
- Peniophorella pubera* (Fr.) P. Karst. – *Hyphoderma puberum* (Fr.) Wallr.; *Phlebia pubera* (Fr.) M.P. Christ. – L—Parmasto (1966: 373), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 484, 1991: 364), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234), Hallenberg *et al.* (2007: 1371). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Prunus* sp., 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15100). Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 4 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA

- 16730). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22593. D—The whole area.
- Phanerochaete aculeata* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Burdsall (1985: 31), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 44), Hjortstam & Ryvarde (2007: 92). E—Iran: Gilan, Fuman, Qale-rud Khan, on a hardwood twig, 2 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 868. D—IRN.
- Phanerochaete avellanea* (Bres.) J. Erikss. & Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- Phanerochaete caucasica* (Parmasto) Burds. – *Ph. cremea* var. *caucasica* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1967: 388, 1968a: 42, 1968b: 219), Burdsall (1985: 55). D—AR, GR.
- Phanerochaete chrysosporium* Burds. – *Ph. macrocystidiata* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Burdsall (1985: 61), Hjortstam & Ryvarde (2007: 93). E—Russia: Dagestan, Magaramkent, Samur Nature Reserve, on *Juglans regia*, 17 Sep 1973, Parmasto (TAA 58235). D—IRN, RUS.
- Phanerochaete cremeo-ochracea* (Bourdot & Galzin) Hjortstam – *Phlebia cremeo-ochracea* (Bourdot & Galzin) Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1968a: 42), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—AZ, RUS.
- Phanerochaete deflectens* (P. Karst.) Hjortstam – *Phlebia deflectens* (P. Karst.) Ryvarde; *Ph. umbrata* (Bourdot & Galzin) Parmasto [incl. var. *lilacea* (M.P. Christ.) Parmasto] – L—Parmasto (1968a: 42), Eriksson *et al.* (1981: 1109). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Akçaabat, under mosses, 27 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 13283. D—AR, AZ, TUR.
- Phanerochaete filamentosa* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Burds. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS. However, according to Greslebin *et al.* (2004) *Ph. filamentosa* occurs in North America only, and the Eurasian samples belong to *Ph. radicata* (Henn.) Nakasone, C.R. Bergman & Burds.
- Phanerochaete laevis* (Pers.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarde – *Cylindrobasidium laeve* (Pers.) Chamuris; *Peniophora laevis* (Pers.) Burt – L—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 19 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16182). Turkey: Trabzon, on *Rhododendron*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13272. D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR. Burdsall (1985: 90) mentioned a record of this species from Kadzherom for Armenia. Actually, this locality is in Komi Republic.
- Phanerochaete magnoliae* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Burds. – *Ph. radulooides* J. Erikss. & Ryvarde; *Radulum cumulodentatum* Nikol. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Burdsall (1985: 95), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, IRN.
- Phanerochaete martelliana* (Bres.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarde – L—Eriksson *et al.* (1978: 1013), Hallenberg (1981: 487). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Nahar-Khoran, on hardwood twigs, 20 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1346. D—IRN.
- Phanerochaete sanguinea* (Fr.) Pouzar – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 106). D—RUS.
- Phanerochaete sordida* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarde – *Peniophora cremea* (Bres.) Sacc. & Syd. – L—Petra (1940: 427), Saber (1974: 21), Hallenberg (1981: 487), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Georgia: Colchis, Poti, on *Alnus barbata*, 11 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16609). Turkey: Trabzon, Vakfikebir, on *Fagus*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11532. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Phanerochaete subquercina* (Henn.) Hjortstam – *Ph. radulans* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Burdsall (1985: 103), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 46). E—Azerbaijan: Khachmaz, Khachmaz, on *Quercus longipes*, 31 Oct 1981, Parmasto (TAA 104211). D—AZ, IRN.
- Phanerochaete tuberculata* (P. Karst.) Parmasto – *Corticium lacteum* (Fr.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 103), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 326), Hallenberg (1981: 487), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 100), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Qale-darasi, on hardwood branch, 5 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 464. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on hardwood branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11380. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Phanerochaete velutina* (DC.) Parmasto – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Hallenberg (1981: 487), Burdsall (1985: 133), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106, 2005: 234), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Makidi, on *Quercus*, 3 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 412. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on hardwood branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11377. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- **Phanerochaete xerophila* Burds. – E—Russia: Caucasus Nature Reserve, Umpyr', alt. 1200 m, 11 Aug 1976, Puusepp (TAA 109096). D—RUS. Earlier known only from N America.
- Phlebia acerina* Peck – *Ph. meruliooides* Lloyd – L—Nakasone & Sytsma (1993: 999), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 2 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16324). Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Acer velutinum*, 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15960). Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12963. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Phlebia albida* H. Post ex Fr. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Nakasone (1996: 768). E—Russia: Dagestan, Magaramkent, Samur Nature Reserve, on *Populus alba*, 18 Sep 1973, Parmasto (TAA 58283). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jofa, Missan, on *Quercus*, 29 Sep 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 317. Turkey: Trabzon, on *Corylus*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13266. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Phlebia albomellea* (Bondartsev) Nakasone – L—Nakasone (1996: 766). D—IRN.
- Phlebia aurea* (Fr.) Nakasone – *Mycocacia aurea* (Fr.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarde; *Sarcodontia stenodon* (Pers.) Nikol. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 179), Hallenberg (1981: 486),

- Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 443), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Nakasone (1997: 55), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 6 Aug 1974, Puusepp (TAA 90462). D—The whole area.
- Phlebia badia* (Pat.) Nakasone – L—Hallenberg (1981: 486 as *Mycoaciella bispora*), Nakasone (2002: 478). D—IRN.
- Phlebia caspica* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 47). E—Iran: Gilan, Siahkal, on *Fagus orientalis*, 30 Apr 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 820. D—IRN.
- Phlebia centrifuga* P. Karst. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 487), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Greslebin *et al.* (2004: 262). D—IRN, RUS.
- **Phlebia coccineofulva* Schwein. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on deciduous wood, 7 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12035. D—RUS.
- Phlebia diaphana* Parmasto ex K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – L—Hjortstam & Larsson (1986: 440). D—GR.
- Phlebia fuscoatra* (Fr.) Nakasone – *Mycoacia fuscoatra* (Fr.) Donk; *Mycocleptodon fuscoater* (Fr.) Pilát – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 156, 1964: 211), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Nakasone (1997: 59), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Phlebia georgica* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1967: 390), Eriksson *et al.* (1981: 1119). D—GR.
- Phlebia lilascens* (Bourdot) J. Erikss. & Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16240. D—IRN, RUS.
- Phlebia lindtneri* (Pilát) Parmasto – *Ph. merulioidea* Parmasto – L—Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Eriksson *et al.* (1981: 1131), Hallenberg (1981: 487), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 987). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Phlebia livida* (Pers.) Bres. [incl. *Ph. livida* f. *hydnoidea* Parmasto] – L—Woronow (1915: 109), Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 487, 1991: 371), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Hallenberg & Larsson (1993: 353). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 26 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15410). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Phlebia nothofagi* (G. Cunn.) Nakasone – L—Nakasone (1997: 67). D—AZ, GR.
- **Phlebia pulcherrima* Parmasto – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Apsheronsk, Pyatigorsk, on *Populus tremula*, 3 Oct 1966, Parmasto (TAA 18927). D—RUS.
- Phlebia radiata* Fr. – *Ph. aurantiaca* (Sowerby) J. Schröt.; *Ph. contorta* Fr.; *Ph. merismoides* (Fr.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 109), Woronichin (1927: 153), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Melia *et al.* (1987: 114, 155), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 987), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 465), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15569). Azerbaijan: Khachmaz, Khachmaz, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 31 Oct 1981, Parmasto (TAA 104213). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Phlebia rufa* (Pers.) M.P. Christ. – *Merulius phlebioides* Bourdot & Galzin – L—Eriksson *et al.* (1981: 1159), Hallenberg (1981: 487), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 27), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Hallenberg (1991: 372), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234), Nakasone & Sytsma (1993: 1004), Greslebin *et al.* (2004: 263), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 987). D—IRN, RUS, TUR. Nakasone & Systma (1993) stated that the report by Hallenberg (1991) from Turkey may be *Ph. acerina*. They confined *Ph. rufa* to Europe and N America, however enumerated it from Iran (on page 1004).
- Phlebia segregata* (Bourdot & Galzin) Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1978: 71, 1991: 372). D—IRN, TUR.
- Phlebia serialis* (Fr.) Donk – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- **Phlebia subcretacea* (Litsch.) M.P. Christ. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13075. D—RUS.
- Phlebia subochracea* (Bres.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488). D—IRN.
- Phlebia subserialis* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Castanea sativa*, 19 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16360). D—GR, RUS.
- Phlebia tremellosa* (Schröd.) Nakasone & Burds. – *Merulius tremellosus* Schrad. – L—Woronichin (1915a: 14, 1927: 154), Woronow (1915: 112), Singer (1930: 78, 1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 486), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Melia *et al.* (1987: 180, 435), Saber (1987: 29, 2002: 286), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 183), Mukhamedshin (2005: 234), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15507). Azerbaijan: Leriki, on a fallen trunk, 9 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15878). D—The whole area.
- Phlebia uda* (Fr.) Nakasone – *Mycoacia uda* (Fr.) Donk; *Sarcodontia uda* (Fr.) Nikol. – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 183), Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 486, 1991: 368), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 443), Mukhamedshin (1992: 106), Nakasone (1997: 72), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Phlebiella ardosiacae* (Bourdot & Galzin) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – L—Hallenberg (1991: 373). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on trunk of a broad-leaved tree, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13062; Mostovskoy, Psebay, on *Ulmus*, 6 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 11984. D—RUS, TUR.
- Phlebiella borealis* K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on a hardwood branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11371. D—RUS, TUR.
- Phlebiella christiansenii* (Parmasto) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- Phlebiella fibrillosa* (Hallenb.) K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam – *Trechispora fibrillosa* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490), Hjortstam & Ryvarden (2007: 100). D—IRN.

- Phlebiella insperata* (H.S. Jacks.) Oberw. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- Phlebiella sulphurea* (Pers.) Ginns & Lefebvre – *Ph. vaga* (Fr.) P. Karst.; *Trechispora vaga* (Fr.) Libert – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 27 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16272). Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Picea orientalis*, 3 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16655). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16245. Turkey: Trabzon, Çilekli, on *Picea*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11516. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Phlebiella tulasnelloidea* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Bondartsev & Singer – *Xenasma tulasnelloideum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 491), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on *Quercus*, 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15946). Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on *Quercus*, 11 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13008. D—AZ, IRN, RUS.
- *Phlebiopsis gigantea* (Fr.) Jülich – *Peniophora gigantea* (Fr.) Masee; *Phanerochaete gigantea* (Fr.) S.S. Rattan, Abdullah & Ismail; *Phlebia gigantea* (Fr.) Donk – L—Woronow (1915: 104), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 30, 114), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: Gilan, Rezvanshahr, on fallen corticated branch of cultivated *Pinus*, 4 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 927a. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Phlebiopsis ravenelii* (Cooke) Hjortstam – *Peniophora moelleriana* (Bres.) Sacc.; *P. subabscondita* (Bres.) Höhn. & Litsch.; *Phlebia roumegueri* (Bres.) Donk; *Phlebiopsis roumegueri* (Bres.) Jülich & Stalpers – L—Woronow (1915: 103, 104), Parmasto (1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 488), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438, also as “*sunascondita*”), Melia *et al.* (1987: 155), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007, also as “*sunascondita*”). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN.
- Piloderma byssinum* (P. Karst.) Jülich – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 233), Zmitrovich (2008: 191). D—RUS.
- Piloderma fallax* (Liberta) Stalpers – *P. bicolor* (Peck) Jülich – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 233). D—RUS.
- *Plicatura nivea* (Sommerf.) P. Karst. – *Merulius niveus* Fr. – L—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 89). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, on fallen hardwood branch, 11 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1222. Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on *Alnus*, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13057. D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Plicaturopsis crispa* (Pers.) D.A. Reid – *Plicatura crispa* (Pers.) Rea; *P. faginea* (Schr.) P. Karst.; *Trogia crispa* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 125 as *Trogia faginea* (Schr.) Schroet.), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 23), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 34), Melia *et al.* (1987: 109, 192 as *Trogia faginea* Schroet.), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). E—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on a fallen twig, 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15942). Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Psebay, on *Alnus*, 6 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 11973. D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- * *Porostereum crassum* (Lév.) Hjortstam & Ryvarden – E—Iran: Gilan, Rezvanshahr, on a dead, hardwood stump, 4 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 938. D—IRN.
- Porostereum spadiceum* (Pers.) Hjortstam & Ryvarden – *Lloydella spadicea* (Pers.) Bres.; *Lopharia spadicea* (Pers.) Boidin; *Stereum spadiceum* (Pers.) Quél. – L—Woronichin (1915b: 114, 1927: 151), Woronow (1915: 106), Akhundov (1979: 129), Davydina (1980: 93), Hallenberg (1981: 485), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Kotlaba (1986: 226), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: East Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, on *Populus*, 6 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 486. D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Pseudomerulius aureus* (Fr.) Jülich – *Merulius aureus* Fr. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234). D—RUS.
- * *Radulodon erikssonii* Ryvarden – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Slavyansk, on hardwood, 28 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 19789). D—RUS.
- Radulomyces confluens* (Fr.) M.P. Christ. – *Cerocorticium confluens* (Fr.) Jülich & Stalpers – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 405), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2007: 109). E—Armenia: Syunik, Kafan, on *Rhamnus cathartica*, 2 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16213). Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, on *Buxus colchica*, 17 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16335). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Radulomyces molaris* (Chaillat ex Fr.) M.P. Christ. – *Radulum molare* Chaillat ex Fr.; *R. rude* (Pers.) S. Lundell – L—Woronow (1915: 109), Woronichin (1927: 153), Nikolajeva (1961: 83), Hallenberg (1981: 488), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2007: 110), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16248). Russia: Krasnodar, near Anapa, on *Robinia pseudoacacia*, 16 Jul 2000, Shiryayev (SVER 58038). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Radulomyces rickii* (Bres.) M.P. Christ. – L—Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2007: 104). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Juniperus polycarpus*, 28 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15476). D—AR, IRN.
- Radulomyces roseolus* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1968b: 222). D—GR.
- Repetobasidium mirificum* J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1991: 374). D—TUR.
- Resinicium bicolor* (Alb. & Schwein.) Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1991: 374), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 988). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12119. D—RUS, TUR.
- * *Resinicium furfuraceum* (Bres.) Parmasto – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on a fallen trunk of *Castanea*, 8 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12918. D—RUS.

- Sarcodontia crocea* (Schwein.) Kotl. – *S. mali* Schulzer – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 177), Popushoy (1971: 201), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Sarcodontia setosa* (Pers.) Donk – L—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR.
- Scopuloides hydroides* (Cooke & Masee) Hjortstam & Ryvarde – *Odontia hydroides* (Cooke & Masee) Höhn.; *Phlebia hydroides* (Cooke & Masee) M.P. Christ. [incl. f. *squalida* Parmasto] – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 132), Parmasto (1966: 373, 1967: 390), Hallenberg (1981: 488), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Saber (1987: 29), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234). E—Armenia: Tavush, Kirovakan, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 19 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15102). Azerbaijan: Leriki, on a fallen twig, 11 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15954). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22556. Turkey: Rize, S of Çamlıhemşin, on *Alnus*, 5 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11427. D—The whole area.
- **Scopuloides leprosa* (Bourdot & Galzin) Boidin, Lanq. & Gilles – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on log of a broad-leaved tree, 16 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13108. D—RUS.
- Scytinostroma aluta* Lanq. – L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 137), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 281). D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Scytinostroma galactinum* (Fr.) Donk – L—Parmasto (1970: 52), Hallenberg (1981: 491), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Hallenberg & Küffer (2001: 432). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Scytinostroma ochroleucum* (Bres. & Torrend) Donk – L—Parmasto (1970: 50), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 140). D—GR, RUS.
- Scytinostroma odoratum* (Fr.) Donk – L—Parmasto (1970: 58), Hallenberg (1981: 491, 1985: 31), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 141). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Scytinostroma portentosum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Donk – *S. hemidichophyticum* Pouzar – L—Parmasto (1970: 62, 65), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 139). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Naharkhoran, on decorticated hardwood branch, 29 Oct 2007, coll. Sohrabi (Ghobad-Nejhad 652). D—IRN, RUS.
- **Scytinostroma praestans* (H.S. Jacks.) Donk – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on a branch of *Fagus*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12156. D—RUS.
- **Scytinostromella heterogenea* (Bourdot & Galzin) Parmasto – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on a fallen log of *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12103. D—RUS.
- Scytinostromella olivaceoalba* (Bourdot & Galzin) Ginns & Lefebvre – *Confertobasidium olivaceoalbum* (Bourdot & Galzin) Jülich s. auct. – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 105). D—RUS.
- Serpula himantioides* (Fr.) Bondartsev – *Merulius squalidus* Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 112). D—RUS.
- Serpula lacrymans* (Wulfen) J. Schröt. – *S. destruens* (Pers.) Gray; *S. domestica* (Falck) Bondartsev – L—Woronow (1915: 112), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Simonyan (1981: 150), Arzumanyan (1982: 44, 1986: 16), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 443), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 91), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234), Nikolayev (2001: 99), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- **Sistotrema athelioides* Hallenb. – E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea* stump, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11589. D—TUR.
- Sistotrema brinkmannii* (Bres.) J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488, 1991: 375), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Larsson & Larsson (2003: 1042), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 988). D—AZ, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Sistotrema camshadalicum* Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488). D—IRN.
- Sistotrema coroniferum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488). D—IRN.
- Sistotrema diademiferum* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Makidi, on *Carpinus*, 3 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 408. Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12145. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on a *Picea* stump, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11318. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- **Sistotrema eximum* (H.S. Jacks.) Ryvarde & Solheim – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22560. D—RUS. Apparently, earlier known only from N America.
- Sistotrema oblongisporum* M.P. Christ. & Hauerslev – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488, 1991: 376), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Sistotrema octosporum* (J. Schröt. ex Höhn. & Litsch.) Hallenb. – *S. commune* J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on hardwood twig, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11580. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Sistotrema raduloides* (P. Karst.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488). E—Russia: Krasnodar, on *Populus tremula*, 1 Oct 1966, Parmasto (TAA 19833). D—IRN, RUS.
- Sistotrema resinicystidium* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 488), Hjortstam & Larsson (1994: 57), Hjortstam & Ryvarde (2007: 112). D—IRN.
- Sistotrema suballantosporum* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 489), Eriksson *et al.* (1984: 1363). D—IRN.
- Sistotremastrum niveocreum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) J. Erikss. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 489, 1991: 377), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16220. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- **Sphaerobasidium minutum* (J. Erikss.) Oberw. ex Jülich – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1400 m, on a fallen trunk of *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12087. D—RUS.
- Steccherinum bourdotii* Saliba & A. David – L—Hallenberg (1991: 378). E—Iran: Gilan, Lahijan, Atakuh, on

- Carpinus betulus*, 1 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 825. Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on *Carpinus*, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13051. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Steccherinum fimbriatum* (Pers.) J. Erikss. — *Mycoleptodon fimbriatus* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin, *Odontia fimbriatum* Pers. — L—Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Nikolajeva (1961: 149), Hallenberg (1981: 489), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Saber (1987: 29), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Fagus orientalis*, 16 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15328). Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Fagus orientalis*, 4 Aug 1974, I. Parmasto (TAA 90366). Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on a trunk, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11342. D—The whole area.
- **Steccherinum gilvum* Maas Geest. — L—Hallenberg (1981: 489 as *S. ochraceum*, NH 1289). D—IRN. Earlier known only from the type locality, Japan.
- Steccherinum laeticolor* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Banker — *Mycoleptodon laeticolor* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Pat. — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 146), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—AR, AZ, RUS.
- **Steccherinum murashkinskyi* (Burt) Maas Geest. — *Mycoleptodon murashkinskyi* (Burt) Pilát — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 159), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: Gilan, Asalem, Gisum, alt. -12 m, on a fallen branch of cf. *Alnus*, 4 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 956. D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Steccherinum ochraceum* (Pers.) S.F. Gray — *Hydnum ochraceum* Pers.; *H. pudorinum* Fr.; *Mycoleptodon ochraceus* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin — L—Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 110), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Nikolajeva (1961: 140), Hallenberg (1981: 489, 1991: 378), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Saber (1987: 29), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 354), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Steccherinum queletii* (Bourdot & Galzin) Hallenb. & Hjortstam — *Odontia queletii* Bourdot & Galzin; *Phlebia queletii* (Bourdot & Galzin) M.P. Christ. — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 134), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- Steccherinum rhois* (Schwein.) Banker — *Mycoleptodon rhois* (Schwein.) Nikol. — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 143). D—RUS.
- Steccherinum robustius* (J. Erikss. & S. Lundell) J. Erikss. — *Mycoleptodon laeticolor* f. *robustior* Nikol. — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 147), Hallenberg (1981: 489). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Acer*, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22534. D—AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Steccherinum subcrinale* (Peck) Ryvarden — *Mycoleptodon kavinae* Pilát — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 152). D—W Transcaucasus.
- **Steccherinum tenuispinum* Spirin, Zmitr. & Malysheva — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1700 m, on a fallen trunk of *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12195. D—RUS.
- Stereum gausapatum* (Fr.) Fr. — L—Woronichin (1927: 151), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 337), Davydkina (1980: 74), Hallenberg (1981: 489), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Saber (1987: 29), Melia *et al.* (1987: 161, 190), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 233), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 183), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Vaighan, on hardwood stump, 2 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 398. D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR, W Transcaucasus.
- Stereum hirsutum* (Willd.) Pers. — L—Rabenhorst (1871: 23), Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 316), Filarszky (1907: 15), Woronichin (1915a: 14, 1916: 16, 1927: 151), Woronow (1915: 106), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Singer (1930: 77, 1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Flerov (1962: 117), Morochkovskaya (1968: 202), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 327), Saber (1974: 13), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 34), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 107), Davydkina (1980: 65), Shainidze (1980: 211), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 489), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Melia *et al.* (1987: 78, 98, 161, 191, 503), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 91), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 233), Sesli (1999: 96, 2007: 86), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 75), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 183), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 478), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—The whole area.
- Stereum ochraceoflavum* (Schwein.) Sacc. — L—Davydkina (1980: 69), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324). E—Armenia: Tavush, Stepanavan, on *Quercus macranthera*, 23 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15566). Turkey: Trabzon, Uçarsu, on *Alnus* branch, 9 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11478. D—AR, AZ, RUS, TUR, W Transcaucasus.
- Stereum ostrea* (Blume & T. Nees) Fr. — *S. insignitum* Qué.; *S. fasciatum* (Schwein.) Fr.; *S. ochraceum* Lloyd — L—Woronow (1908: 46, 1915: 107), Woronichin (1927: 151), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 327), Davydkina (1980: 70), Hallenberg (1981: 489), Kotlaba (1985a: 8), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Melia *et al.* (1987: 98, 191), Saber (1987: 29, 2000: 374), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 1992: 107, 2005: 236), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 91), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Stereum rameale* (Pers.) Fr. — L—Hallenberg (1981: 489). D—IRN.
- Stereum rugosum* (Pers.) Fr. — L—Woronow (1908: 46, 1915: 107), Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 337), Davydkina (1980: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Melia *et al.* (1987: 191), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 405), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Rhododendron*, 2–4 Oct

- 1989, Hallenberg 11294. D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR, W Transcaucasus.
- *Stereum sanguinolentum* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 107), Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 329), Davydkina (1980: 77), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 234), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 354), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). E—Iran: Gilan, Rezvanshahr, on CWD of *Pinus*, 4 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 934. D—The whole area.
- Stereum subtomentosum* Pouzar – *S. fasciatum* (Schwein.) Fr. sensu auct. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 35, as *S. fasciatum*), Saber (1974: 15), Davydkina (1980: 68), Hallenberg (1981: 489), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, W Transcaucasus.
- Subulicystidium longisporum* (Pat.) Parmasto – L—Hallenberg (1981: 489). E—Armenia: Tavush, Kirovakan, on *Tilia cordata*, 19 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15108). Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Juglans regia*, 12 Aug 1974, I. Parmasto (TAA 90670). Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Acer trautvetteri*, 4 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16701). Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on *Fraxinus*, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12947. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on a hardwood branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11282. D—The whole area.
- * *Subulicystidium obtusisporum* Duhem & H. Michel – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fraxinus exelsior*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22507. D—RUS.
- * *Subulicystidium perlongisporum* Boidin & Gilles – E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kalibar, Tatar, on hardwood twig, 9 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1111. D—IRN.
- Terana caerulea* (Lam.) Kuntze – *Corticium caeruleum* (Lam.) Fr.; *Pulcherricium caeruleum* (Lam.) Parmasto – L—Woronow (1915: 103), Nagorny (1930: 60), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 326), Hallenberg (1981: 488), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 81), Sesli (1999: 96), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 465), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: “7”), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 289). E—Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Rubus*, 5 Aug 1974, I. Parmasto (TAA 90425). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, TUR.
- Trechispora alnicola* (Bourdot & Galzin) Liberta – *Cristella alnicola* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk; *Grandinia alnicola* Bourdot & Galzin – L—Nikolajeva (1961: 70), Parmasto (1965b: 318), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 489), Hjortstam *et al.* (1988: 1493). D—AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Trechispora candidissima* (Schwein.) Bondartsev & Singer – *Cristella candidissima* (Schwein.) Donk – L—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 324), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 417), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404). E—Russia: Krasnodar, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 16 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 18737). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Trechispora caucasica* (Parmasto) Liberta – *Cristella caucasica* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1965a: 221, 1965b: 318), Larsson (1996: 75), Miettinen & Larsson (2006: 198). D—AZ.
- Trechispora cohaerens* (Schwein.) Jülich & Stalpers – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Fagus*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12134. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11573. D—RUS, TUR.
- Trechispora confinis* (Bourdot & Galzin) Liberta – L—Hallenberg (1981: 489). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kalaleh, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16243. Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Pinus*, 7 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12017. Turkey: Trabzon, Sumela monastery, on a branch, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11545. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Trechispora dimitica* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490). E—Georgia: Chakva, on *Eucalyptus smithii*, 28 Sep 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16044). Iran: Gilan, Masal, Tiaskuh, on litter, 3 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 923. D—GR, IRN.
- Trechispora farinacea* (Pers.) Liberta – *Hydnum farinaceum* Pers. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Hallenberg (1981: 490), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11577. D—IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Trechispora granulifera* Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490). D—IRN.
- * *Trechispora hymenocystis* (Berk. & Broome) K.H. Larss. – E—Georgia: Imereti, Tkibuli, Kharistvali, on *Fagus orientalis*, 18 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 15203). Russia: Karachayevo-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on *Picea orientalis*, 20 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 53143); Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1400 m, on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12115. D—GR, RUS.
- * *Trechispora invisitata* (H.S. Jacks.) Liberta – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on branch of *Abies*, 20 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13191. D—RUS.
- Trechispora lunata* (Romell ex Bourdot & Galzin) Jülich – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- Trechispora microspora* (P. Karst.) Liberta – L—Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 490), Larsson (1996: 80), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 128). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13036. Turkey: Trabzon, Sumela monastery, on decayed wood, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11581. D—AR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Trechispora mollusca* (Pers.) Liberta – *Fibuloporia mollusca* (Pers.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Poria mollusca* (Pers.) Quél. – L—Woronow (1915: 112), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 122), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 169), Hallenberg (1981: 490), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Melia *et al.* (1987: 189), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001:

- 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Trechispora nivea* (Pers.) K.H. Larss. — *Grandinia nivea* (Pers.) S. Lundell — L—Nikolajeva (1961: 72), Larsson (1995: 110). E—Armenia: Noyemberyan, on *Carpinus orientalis*, 15 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15676). Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jolfa, Missan, on a hardwood log, 29 Sep 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 348. D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Trechispora praefocata* (Bourdot & Galzin) Liberta — L—Hallenberg (1981: 490). D—IRN.
- Trechispora stellulata* (Bourdot & Galzin) Liberta — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Larsson (1996: 77). D—RUS, TUR.
- Trechispora stevensonii* (Berk. & Broome) K.H. Larss. — L—Larsson (1995: 115). E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, Getashen, on *Carpinus caucasica*, 26 Sep 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15407). Turkey: Rize, S of Çamlıhemşin, on *Alnus*, 5 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11417. D—AR, IRN, TUR.
- Trechispora subhelvetica* (Parmasto) Liberta — *Cristella subhelvetica* Parmasto — L—Parmasto (1965a: 223). D—AR.
- **Trechispora tenuicula* (Litsch.) K.H. Larss. — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on a fern, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22531. D—RUS.
- Tubulicium vermiferum* (Bourdot) Oberw. ex Jülich — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Akçaabat, on *Rhododendron*, 27 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13279. D—RUS, TUR.
- **Tubulicrinis accedens* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1000 m, on wood of *Abies*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12148. D—RUS.
- Tubulicrinis cinctus* G. Cunn. — L—Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 282). D—IRN, RUS.
- **Tubulicrinis borealis* J. Erikss. — E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, alt. 1000–1100 m, on a *Picea* log, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11286. D—TUR.
- **Tubulicrinis chaetophorus* (Höhn.) Donk — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1700 m, on a brown-rotted trunk of *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12184. D—RUS.
- **Tubulicrinis confusus* K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam — E—Turkey: Trabzon, Sumela monastery, on a *Picea* log, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11560. D—TUR.
- Tubulicrinis glebulosus* (Fr.) Donk — *Peniophora glebulosa* (Fr.) Sacc.; *Tubulicrinis gracillimus* (Ellis & Everh. ex D.P. Rogers & H.S. Jacks.) G. Cunn. — L—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22589. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11300. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- **Tubulicrinis hamatus* (H.S. Jacks.) Donk — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Umpyr', on *Pinus* sp., 11 Aug 1976, Puusepp (TAA 109089). D—RUS.
- Tubulicrinis incrassatus* Hallenb. — L—Hallenberg (1981: 490), Hjortstam *et al.* (1988: 1537), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 289). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Alangdarreh, on hardwood branches, 19 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1308. D—IRN.
- **Tubulicrinis medius* (Bourdot & Galzin) Oberw. — E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', alt. 1000 m, on *Abies* branch, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12125. D—TUR.
- **Tubulicrinis sororius* (Bourdot & Galzin) Oberw. — E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, alt. 1600 m, on *Picea* branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11301. D—TUR.
- Tubulicrinis strangulatus* K.H. Larss. & Hjortstam — L—Hallenberg (1991: 380). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on a fallen trunk, 13 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12267. D—RUS, TUR.
- Tubulicrinis subulatus* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Georgia: Adjaria, Khulo, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 3 Oct 1963, Parmasto (TAA 16016). Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on *Abies*, 20 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13212; Adygeya, Maykop, on *Pinus*, 16 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22566. D—GR, RUS.
- Tubulicrinis thermometrus* (G. Cunn.) M.P. Christ. — L—Hallenberg (1981: 490). D—IRN.
- Vararia investiens* (Schw.) P. Karst. — L—Parmasto (1970: 79). E—Iran: Ardabil, Andabil, on fallen hardwood twigs under litter, 6 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1022. D—IRN, RUS.
- Vararia ochroleuca* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk — L—Parmasto (1970: 74), Hallenberg (1981: 491), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 146). D—AR, IRN.
- Veluticeps abietina* (Pers.) Hjortstam & Tellería — *Columnocystis abietina* (Pers.) Pouzar; *Stereum abietinum* Fr.; *S. crispum* (Pers.) Quél. — L—Davydkina (1980: 111), Melia *et al.* (1987: 14), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 234), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11355. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Vesiculomyces citrinus* (Pers.) E. Hagstr. — *Gloeocystidiellum radiosum* (Fr.) Boidin — L—Parmasto (1965b: 318), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22515; on *Pinus*, 16 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22570. D—GR, RUS.
- Vuilleminia comedens* (Nees) Maire — L—Woronow (1915: 103), Hallenberg (1981: 490, 1991: 381), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 233), Hallenberg & Parmasto (1998: 642), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 405). E—Armenia: 43 km NNE Yerevan, on trunk bark, 4 Oct 1986, Lundqvist 16446 (S). D—The whole area.
- Vuilleminia coryli* Boidin, Lanq. & Gilles — L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 285). E—Armenia: Yerevan, on *Ulmus* sp., 2 Oct 1986, Strid (S 17912). Russia: Karachayev-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on *Corylus*

- avellana*, 17 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 001). D—AR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Vuilleminia cystidiata* Parmasto – L—Parmasto (1965a: 232, 1966: 373), Hallenberg (1981: 490), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107, 2005: 233). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jolfa, Missan, on *Crataegus*, 29 Sep 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 318. D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Vuilleminia macrospora* (Bres.) Hjortstam – L—Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—RUS.
- Vuilleminia megalospora* Bres. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490). D—IRN.
- **Vuilleminia pseudocystidiata* Boidin, Lanq. & Gilles – E—Armenia: Tavush, Idzhevan, on *Cornus mas*, 16 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15670). D—AR.
- **Xenasma praeteritum* (H.S. Jacks.) Donk – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr^r, alt. 1000 m, on a brown-rotted stump, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12054. D—RUS.
- Xenasma pruinatum* (Pat.) Donk – L—Parmasto (1965b: 318), Hallenberg (1981: 490), Ghobad-Nejhad *et al.* (2008: 290). D—GR, IRN.
- Xenasma pulverulentum* (Litsch.) Donk – L—Hallenberg (1981: 490), Hjortstam *et al.* (1988: 1599), Mukhamedshin (1992: 107). D—IRN, RUS.
- Xylobolus frustulatus* (Pers.) Boidin – *Stereum frustulatum* (Pers.) Fr.; *S. frustulosum* Fr. L—Woronow (1915: 107), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Vasil'eva (1939: 35), Selik (1973: 29), Davydkina (1980: 79), Hallenberg (1981: 491), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Melia *et al.* (1987: 161), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 91), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 478), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Xylobolus subpileatus* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Boidin – *Stereum subpileatum* Berk. & M.A. Curtis – L—Davydkina (1980: 81), Hallenberg (1981: 491), Kotlaba (1985: 199), Saber (2000: 374 as "*Xylopilus*"). D—AZ, IRN.
- L—Hallenberg (1981: 494), Bondartseva (1998: 119). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 12 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13054. D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Albatrellus confluens* (Alb. & Schwein.) Kotl. & Pouzar – *Polyporus confluens* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 39). D—RUS.
- Albatrellus cristatus* (Schaeff.) Kotl. & Pouzar – *Polyporus cristatus* (Schaeff.) Fr.; *Scutigera cristatus* (Schaeff.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Woronow (1915: 117), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 599), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 443), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83), Bondartseva (1998: 43), Sesli (1998: 46), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 470), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: "13"). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Albatrellus ovinus* (Schaeff.) Kotl. & Pouzar – *Scutigera ovinus* (Schaeff.) Murrill – L—Bondarzew (1953: 601), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 103), Bondartseva (1998: 44), Nikolayev (2001: 99). D—AR, RUS.
- Amauroderma rude* (Berk.) Torrend – *Polyporus rudis* Berk. – L—Hüseyn & Selçuk (2001: 404). D—AZ.
- Anomoporia bombycina* (Fr.) Pouzar – *Fibuloporia bombycina* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer ex Bondartsev – L—Bondarzew (1953: 124), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105), Bondartseva (1998: 124), Hüseyn & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Antrodia albida* (Fr.) Donk – *Coriolellus albidus* (Fr.) Bondartsev; *Trametes sepium* Berk. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 504), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 296), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Bondartseva (1998: 131), Hüseyn & Selçuk (2001: 403), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181). D—The whole area.
- Antrodia heteromorpha* (Fr.) Donk – *Coriolellus heteromorphus* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer; *C. serpens* (Fr.) Bondartsev; *Trametes heteromorpha* (Fr.) Bres. – L—Nikolajeva (1938: 403), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 510, 513), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 298), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 430), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Bondartseva (1998: 136), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Antrodia macra* (Sommerf.) Niemelä – *Coriolellus salicinus* (Bres.) Bondartsev – L—Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 300). D—AR.
- Antrodia serialis* (Fr.) Donk – *Coriolellus serialis* (Fr.) Murrill; *Trametes serialis* (Fr.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 150, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 122), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 297), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 78), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 430), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Solak *et al.* (2007: 38). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11569. D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.

Polypores

- Abortiporus biennis* (Bull.) Singer [incl. *A. biennis* f. *terrestris* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin] – *Daedalea biennis* (Bull.) Fr.; *Heteroporus biennis* (Bull.) Lázaro Ibiza; *Polyporus biennis* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 117), Nagorny (1930: 68), Pilát (1937: 118), Bondarzew (1953: 537, 541), Kanygina (1964: 42), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 307), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 5), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Saber (1987: 23, 2000: 374), Demirel (1999: 407), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 470), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, on *Carpinus*, Oct 2007, coll. Sohrabi (Ghobad-Nejhad 702); Tehran, on *Fraxinus excelsior*, 25 Sep 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 520. D—The whole area. Both examined specimens are anamorph, *Sporotrichopsis terrestris* (Schulzer) Stalpers.
- Abortiporus fractipes* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Gilb. & Ryvardeen – *Heteroporus fractipes* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) O. Fidalgo

- Antrodia sinuosa* (Fr.) P. Karst. – *Coriolus sinuosus* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer; *C. vaporarius* auct.; *Coriolellus vaporarius* auct.; *Polyporus vaporarius* auct.; *Poria vaporaria* auct. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 113), Bondarzew (1953: 495, 496), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 293, 294), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 33, 160), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 98), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Antrodia xantha* (Fr.) Ryvarden – *Amyloporia xantha* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer ex Bondartsev – L—Bondarzew (1953: 153), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 180), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 78), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 106), Simonyan (1981: 150), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 322), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Antrodiella faginea* Vampola & Pouzar – L—Spirin & Zmitrovich (2003: 70). D—RUS.
- Antrodiella foliaceodentata* (Nikol.) Gilb. & Ryvarden – *Irpex foliaceodentatus* Nikol. – L—Nikolajeva (1949a: 87, 1953: 188, 1961: 170), Bondarzew (1953: 555), Bondartseva (1998: 151), Spirin & Zmitrovich (2003: 72). D—RUS.
- **Antrodiella fragrans* (A. David & Tortič) A. David & Tortič – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on branch of a broad-leaved tree, 10 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 12984. D—RUS.
- Antrodiella romellii* (Donk) Niemelä – *Poria byssina* Romell; *P. romellii* Donk – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 35). D—RUS.
- Antrodiella semisupina* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Ryvarden – *Aporpium semisupinum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Bondartsev; *Tyromyces semisupinus* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Murrill – L—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 210), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, IRN, GR. Fide Miettinen *et al.* (2006), these records may be *Antrodiella pallescens* (Pilát) Niemelä & Miettinen.
- Antrodiella serpula* (P. Karst.) Spirin & Niemelä – *Coriolus hoehnelii* (Bres.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Bondarzew (1953: 490), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 290), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Bondartseva (1998: 151), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Aurantiporus alborubescens* (Bourdot & Galzin) H. Jahn – *Phaeolus alborubescens* Bourdot & Galzin; *Tyromyces alborubescens* (Bourdot & Galzin) Bondartsev – L—Martirosyan (1965: 130), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 211), Fallahyan (1973: 214), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Bondartseva (1998: 336). D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Auriporia aurulenta* A. David, Tortič & Jelić – L—Kummer (2007: 148, 154, 201). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Vostochnoye, on *Picea orientalis*, 8 Aug 1989, Mukhamedshin (TAA 166352); Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on a fallen coniferous log, 7 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12041. D—RUS.
- Bjerkandera adusta* (Willd.) P. Karst. [incl. *B. adusta* f. *crispa* (Pers.) Bondartsev and f. *resupinata* (Bourdot & Galzin) Domański, Orlos & Skirg.] – *Leptoporus adustus* (Willd.) Quél.; *Polyporus adustus* (Willd.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Bondarzew (1912: 112, 1924: 3, 1953: 236), Woronichin (1915b: 115), Woronow (1915: 118), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Singer (1930: 82, 1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Mehdiava (1958: 12), Kanygina (1964: 38), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 197, 199), Saber (1972: 23, 1974: 25, 1987: 23, 2002: 286), Fallahyan (1973: 214), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 336), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Melia *et al.* (1987: 95, 186, 353), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Kazemzade *et al.* (1990: 103), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96, 1999: 129), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Türkekul (2003: 315), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 470), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—The whole area.
- Bjerkandera fumosa* (Pers.) P. Karst. – *Leptoporus imberbis* (Bull.) Quél.; *Polyporus alligatus* Fr.; *P. imberbis* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 118), Bondarzew (1924: 3, 1953: 240), Singer (1930: 82), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Kanygina (1964: 38), Akhundov (1979: 129), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Melia *et al.* (1987: 74), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Boletopsis leucomelaena* (Pers.) Fayod – L—Bondarzew (1953: 612), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 90), Nanagulyan & Senn-Irlet (2002: 2), Nanagulyan (2006: 2). D—AR, AZ.
- Bondarceomyces taxi* (Bondartsev) Parmasto – *Hapalopilus taxi* Bondartsev; *Parmastomyces taxi* (Bondartsev) Y.C. Dai & Niemelä; *Polyporus taxi* Bondartsev, *Tyromyces taxi* (Bondartsev) Ryvarden & Gilb. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1940: 17, 1953: 267), Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 184), Bondartseva (1998: 222), Parmasto & Parmasto (1999: 222). D—RUS.
- Bondarzewia mesenterica* (Schaeff.) Kreisel – *B. montana* (Quél.) Singer; *Polyporus berkeleyi* Fr.; *P. montanus* (Quél.) Ferry – L—Singer (1930: 81, 1931: 518), Solovjev (1932: 121), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Vakin & Shtraukh (1950: 204), Bondarzew (1953: 608), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 334), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 37), Bondartseva (1998: 60), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Kummer (2007: 145, 149, 202). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22653. D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Byssoporia mollicula* (Bourdot) Larsen & Zak – *Byssoporia terrestris* (DC.) M.J. Larsen & Zak; *Poria terrestris* Pers. – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Mukhamedshin (1992: 105, 2005: 233). D—RUS.

- Ceriporia alachuana* (Murrill) Hallenb. – L—Hallenberg (1981: 492). D—IRN.
- Ceriporia aurantiocarnescens* (Henning) M. Pieri & B. Rivoire – *C. viridans* f. *aurantiocarnescens* (Henn.) Domański – L—Bondarzew (1953: 141). D—GR.
- **Ceriporia camaresiana* (Bourdote & Galzin) Bondartsev & Singer – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Lazarevskaya, on *Carpinus*, 8 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12908. D—RUS.
- Ceriporia excelsa* (S. Lundell) Parmasto – *C. rhodella* (Fr.) Donk – L—Bondarzew (1953: 142), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95), Bondartseva (1998: 345). D—AR, IRN, RUS.
- Ceriporia purpurea* (Fr.) Donk – *Merulioporia purpurea* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Meruliopsis purpurea* (Fr.) Bondartsev – L—Bondarzew (1953: 595), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 331), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 105), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Alnus*, 12 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12214. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Ceriporia reticulata* (Hoffm.) Domański – *Fibuloporia reticulata* (Hoffm.) Bondartsev – L—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 170), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403, 404). E—Turkey: Rize, S of Çamlıhemşin, on *Alnus*, 5 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11405. D—AR, AZ, IRN, TUR.
- **Ceriporia spissa* (Schwein. ex Fr.) Rajchenb. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Gelendzhik, on *Quercus petraea*, 24 Sep 1966, Parmasto (TAA 18852). D—RUS.
- Ceriporia subpudorina* (Pilát) Bondartsev – L—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 177), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403). D—AR, AZ.
- Ceriporia viridans* (Berk. & Broome) Donk – L—Bondarzew (1953: 139), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 175), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN.
- Ceriporiopsis aneirina* (Sommerf.) Domański – *Tyromyces aneirinus* (Sommerf.) Ryvarden – L—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Saber (1987: 26), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, IRN.
- Ceriporiopsis gilvescens* (Bres.) Domański – *Ceriporia gilvescens* (Bres.) Donk; *Tyromyces gilvescens* (Bres.) Ryvarden – L—Bondarzew (1953: 143), Martirosyan (1965: 132), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 176), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 5), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95), Bondartseva (1998: 162), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Novorossiysk, Dzhankhot, on *Pinus pityusa*, 5 Oct 2003, Shiryaev (SVER 58025); Adygeya, Maykop, on *Fagus*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22587; on *Acer* sp., 18 Sep, Kotiranta 22624. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Cerrena unicolor* (Bull.) Murrill [incl. *C. unicolor* f. *irpicoides* (Bres.) Domański, Orlos & Skirg., var. *irpicoides* (Bourdote & Galzin) Bondartsev, and f. *resupinata* Weinm.] – *Daedalea cinerea* Fr.; *D. unicolor* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 123), Woronichin (1927: 160), Singer (1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 476), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Kanygina (1964: 40, 41), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 284, 285), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 5), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429), Melia *et al.* (1987: 138, 167, 168, 429), Saber (1987: 23, 2000: 374), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 98, 1999: 129), Asef & Tavanaii (2004: 473, as *Trichaptum abietinum*), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 470), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Cinereomyces lenis* (P. Karst.) Spirin – *Amyloporia lenis* (P. Karst.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Antrodia lenis* (P. Karst.) Ryvarden; *Poria lenis* (P. Karst.) Sacc.; *Skeletocutis lenis* (P. Karst.) Niemelä – L—Singer (1931: 516), Bondarzew (1953: 149), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 178), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 418), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Niemelä & Dai (1997: 137), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Cinereomyces lindbladii* (Berk.) Jülich – *Antrodia lindbladii* (Berk.) Ryvarden; *Poria cinerascens* Bres.; *Tyromyces cinerascens* (Bres.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Bondarzew (1953: 229), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on hardwood branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11378. D—GR, IRN, TUR.
- Cinereomyces vulgaris* (Fr.) Spirin – *Poria vulgaris* (Fr.) Cooke; *Skeletocutis vulgaris* (Fr.) Niemelä & Y.C. Dai – L—Woronow (1915: 112), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 181), Hallenberg (1981: 495 as *Poria lenis*), Melia *et al.* (1987: 97), Niemelä & Dai (1997: 135). D—AR, GR, IRN.
- Climacocystis borealis* (Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar – *Abortiporus borealis* (Fr.) Singer; *Polyporus borealis* Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 119), Woronichin (1927: 157), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 542), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Melia *et al.* (1987: 18), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 80). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11352. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Coltricia cinnamomea* (Jacq.) Murrill – L—Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 184), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 53), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Coltricia perennis* (L.) Murrill – *Polystictus perennis* (L.) Fr., *Polyporus perennis* (L.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 120), Singer (1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 416), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Nakhutsrishvili

- (1986: 430), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Corioloropsis floccosa* (Jungh.) Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 493). D—IRN.
- Daedalea quercina* (L.) Pers. [incl. *D. quercina* f. *trametea* Bourdot & Galzin] – *Lenzites quercina* (L.) P. Karst.; *Trametes quercina* (L.) Pilát – L—Weinmann (1836: 341), Rabenhorst (1871: 24), Hollós (1902: 150, 1905: 319), Filarszky (1907: 16), Bondarzew (1912: 116, 1953: 566), Woronichin (1915a: 14, 1916: 17, 1927: 159), Woronow (1915: 123), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Singer (1930: 78, 1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Teterevnikova-Babayan (1958: 26), Kanygina (1964: 41), Bagdasarova (1965: 67), Martirosyan (1965: 130), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 314, 315), Saber (1972: 25), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 337), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 6), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 36), Akhundov (1979: 129), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Melia *et al.* (1987: 119, 142, 168), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Sesli (1999: 97, 2007: 80), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 471), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Daedaleopsis confragosa* (Bolton) J. Schröt. [incl. *D. confragosa* f. *rubescens* (Alb. & Schwein. Ljub., f. *sibirica* (P. Karst.) Bondarzew, and f. *bulliardii* Donk] – *Daedalea confragosa* (Bolton) Pers.; *D. rubescens* Alb. & Schwein.; *Trametes bulliardii* (Fr.) Fr.; *T. rubescens* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 121, 1916: 257), Woronichin (1927: 160), Nikolajeva (1938: 407, 422, 429), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 569, 572), Kanygina (1964: 42), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 315), Saber (1972: 24), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 37), Akhundov (1979: 129), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Melia *et al.* (1987: 82, 101, 142, 168, 191, 192, 344), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 99), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 471), Mukhamedshin (2005: 235), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Sesli (2007: 80). D—The whole area.
- Daedaleopsis tricolor* (Bull.) Bondartsev & Singer – *D. confragosa* var. *tricolor* (Bull.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Lenzites tricolor* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Bondarzew (1912: 116, 1953: 571), Woronow (1915: 123), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Woronichin (1927: 160), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Kanygina (1964: 42), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 317), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Saber (1987: 23), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS. It is possible that some or the all collections of this species from the Caucasus area are conspecific with *D. confragosa*.
- Datronia mollis* (Sommerf.) Donk – *Antrodia mollis* (Sommerf.) P. Karst.; *Trametes mollis* (Sommerf.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 122), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 525), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 305), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Melia *et al.* (1987: 192), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Sesli (1999: 97, 2007: “7”), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 471), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Azerbaijan: Zakataly Reserve, on *Tilia caucasica*, 9 Aug 1974, I. Parmasto (TAA 90556). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Datronia scutellata* (Schwein.) Gilb. & Ryvarden – *Fomitopsis nigrescens* (Bres.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR.
- Datronia stereoides* (Fr.) Ryvarden – *Antrodia stereoides* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Trametes stereoides* (Fr.) Bres. – L—Woronow (1915: 122), Singer (1931: 517), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Bondartseva (1998: 183), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- *Dichomitus campestris* (Quél.) Domański & Orlicz – *Coriolellus campestris* (Quél.) Bondartsev; *Trametes campestris* Quél. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 515), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 300), Simonyan (1981: 150), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 430), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Bondartseva (1998: 186), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Makidi, on *Quercus*, 3 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 423; Gilan, Asalem, on fallen twig of deciduous tree, 5 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 986. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Dichomitus squalens* (P. Karst.) D.A. Reid – *Coriolellus squalens* (P. Karst.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Bondarzew (1953: 507), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Diplomitoporus flavescens* (Bres.) Domański – *Coriolellus flavescens* (Bres.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Trametes flavescens* Bres. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 418), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 430), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Favolus europaeus* Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 124). D—GR.
- Fibroporia destructor* (Schr.) Parmasto – *Polyporus destructor* (Schr.) Fr.; *Tyromyces destructor* (Schr.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Woronow (1915: 118), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR.
- Fibroporia gossypium* (Speg.) Parmasto – *Tyromyces resupinatus* (Bourdot & Galzin) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Martirosyan (1963: 66, 1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 200), Simonyan (1981: 150), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129). D—AR.
- Fibroporia vaillantii* (DC.) Parmasto – *Antrodia vaillantii* (DC.) Ryvarden; *Fibuloporia vaillantii* (DC.) Bondartsev

- & Singer ex Bondartsev – L—Bondarzew (1953: 119), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 168), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 78), Simonyan (1981: 150), Arzumanyan (1982: 44, 1986: 16), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Fistulina hepatica* (Schaeff.) With. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronichin (1915b: 115, 1927: 160), Woronow (1915: 124), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 614), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 335), Hallenberg (1981: 499), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 28), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 34), Melia *et al.* (1987: 145, 171), Saber (1987: 30, 2000: 374), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95), Bondartseva (1998: 72), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 99), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 180), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—The whole area.
- Flaviporus brownei* (Humb.) Donk – L—Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Bondartseva (1998: 198). **D**—RUS.
- Fomes fomentarius* (L.) J.J. Kickx – *Polyporus fomentarius* (L.) Fr., *Ungulina fomentaria* (L.) Pat. – L—Speshnev (1897: 218), Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1908: 46, 1915: 115), Bondarzew (1912: 113, 1953: 284), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1916: 16, 1927: 155), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Singer (1930: 79, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Mehdiya (1958: 12), Flerov (1962: 117), Kanygina (1964: 39, 1972: 181), Bagdasarova (1965: 67), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 221), Saber (1972: 27, 1974: 25, 1987: 23, 2000: 374, 2002: 286), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 673, 1976: 7), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 37), Akhundov (1979: 130), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Altan *et al.* (1986: 31), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 432), Melia *et al.* (1987: 58, 70, 85, 112, 145, 159, 171, 186, 199, 265), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Sesli (1999: 97), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Demirel & Uzun (2002: 292), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Türkekül (2003: 315), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 471), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 145, 202), Sesli (2007: 80). **D**—The whole area.
- Fomitiporia hartigii* (Allesch. & Schnabl) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Phellinus hartigii* (Allesch. & Schnabl) Pat., *Fomes robustus* f. *hartigii* (Allesch. & Schnabl) Bondartsev, *F. robustus* f. *pinus* Bres. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Vakın & Shtraukh (1950: 203), Bondarzew (1953: 365), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 97), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Kummer (2007: 145, 202). **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22580. **D**—RUS.
- Fomitiporia hippophaëicola* (H. Jahn) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Phellinus robustus* f. *hippophaës* Donk – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Russia: Dagestan, on *Hippophae rhamnoides*, 8 May 1974, Parmasto (TAA 581746). **D**—AZ, GR, RUS.
- **Fomitiporia pseudopunctata* (A. David, Dequatre & Fiasson) Fiasson – **E**—Russia: Dagestan, Dzhavgat, on *Fagus orientalis*, 13 Sep 1973, Parmasto (TAA 58171); Magaramkent, Samur Nature Reserve, on *Pyrus caucasica*, 17 Sep 1973, Parmasto (TAA 58118). **D**—RUS.
- Fomitiporia punctata* (P. Karst.) Murrill – *Fuscoporia punctata* (Fr.) G. Cunn.; *Phellinus punctatus* (Fr.) Pilát – L—Bondarzew (1953: 402), Martirosyan (1964: 83), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 256), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 9), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 30), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 206), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Azerbaijan: Astara, Mashkhan, on *Buxus hyrcana*, 20 May 1977, Parmasto (TAA 100674). **D**—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Fomitiporia robusta* (P. Karst.) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Phellinus robustus* (P. Karst.) Bourdot & Galzin [incl. var. *buxi* Bourdot & Galzin]; *Polyporus buxi* Branke – L—Branke (1894: 473), Bondarzew (1953: 361, 364), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 244), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 9), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 30), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 118), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 94), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Fomitopsis cajanderi* (P. Karst.) Kotl. & Pouzar – L—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100). **D**—AR.
- Fomitopsis epileucina* (Pilát) Gilb. & Ryvarden – L—Bondartseva (1998: 203). **D**—AR, GR.
- Fomitopsis iberica* Melo & Ryvarden – *Pilatoporus ibericus* (Melo & Ryvarden) Kotl. & Pouzar – L—Vampola (1996: 87), Spirin & Zmitrovich (2003: 79), Spirin *et al.* (2006: 78). **D**—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Fomitopsis pinicola* (Sw.) P. Karst. – *Fomes marginatus* (Pers.) Fr.; *F. unguatus* (Schaeff.) Sacc.; *Polyporus cinnamomeus* Trog; *P. marginatus* (Pers.) Fr.; *P. pinicola* (Sw.) Fr.; *Ungulina marginata* (Fr.) Pat.; *U. pinicola* (Sw.) Singer – L—Buhse (1860: 245), Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17, 18), Bondarzew (1912: 113, 1953: 293), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1927: 156), Woronow (1915: 114), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Singer (1930: 79, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Pilát (1940: 351), Flerov (1962: 117), Kanygina (1964: 39), Bagdasarova (1965: 67), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 223), Saber (1972: 28), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 673, 1976: 7), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Klán & Kotilová-

- Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 16, 27, 85, 172, 173, 305, 319, 350, 456), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 471), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 148, 151, 202), Sesli (2007: 80). D—The whole area.
- Fomitopsis rosea*** (Alb. & Schwein.) P. Karst. – *Fomes roseus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr.; *Ungulina rosea* (Alb. & Schwein.) Pat. – L—Woronow (1915: 116), Woronichin (1927: 156), Singer (1930: 79, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 290), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 16), Hallenberg (1991: 360), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Fomitopsis spraguei*** (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Gilb. & Ryvar den – Asef (pers. comm., 2009). D—IRN.
- Funalia gallica*** (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer [incl. *F. gallica* f. *resupinato-reflexa* Bourdot & Galzin and f. *tenuis* Bourdot & Galzin] – *Corioloopsis gallica* (Fr.) Ryvar den; *Trametes hispida* Bagl. – L—Bondarzew (1912: 115, 1953: 529, 530, 531), Woronow (1915: 122), Nikolajeva (1938: 400), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Kanygina (1964: 41), Khabiri (1968: 138), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Saber (1987: 23, 2000: 374), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Bondartseva (1998: 171), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Funalia trogii*** (Berk.) Bondartsev & Singer [incl. *F. trogii* f. *mollis-hirsuta* (Nikol.) Domański] – *Corioloopsis trogii* (Berk.) Domański; *Trametes trogii* Berk. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1915b: 115, 1927: 159), Woronow (1915: 121), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 531), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 306), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 337), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Saber (1987: 26, 2000: 374, 2002: 286), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 99), Demirel & Uzun (2002: 292), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 30), Türkekül (2003: 315), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Fuscoporia contigua*** (Pers.) G. Cunn. – *Phellinus contiguus* (Pers.) Pat.; *Ph. ferruginosus* subsp. *floccosus* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin; *Poria contigua* (Pers.) P. Karst. – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Woronichin (1927: 154), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 403, 408), Martirosyan (1964: 84), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 258), Popushoy (1971: 220), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 91), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 207), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Fuscoporia ferrea*** (Pers.) G. Cunn. – *Phellinus ferreus* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Martirosyan (1964: 85), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 262), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 93). D—AR.
- Fuscoporia ferruginosa*** (Schrad.) Murrill – *Phellinus ferruginosus* (Schrad.) Pat.; *Poria ferruginosa* (Schrad.) P. Karst. – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Woronichin (1916: 16), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Pilát (1942: 541), Bondarzew (1953: 405), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 259), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 10), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 95), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Melia *et al.* (1987: 401), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 208), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 38). D—The whole area.
- Fuscoporia gilva*** (Schwein.) T. Wagner & M. Fisch. – *Phellinus gilvus* (Schwein.) Pat. – L—Martirosyan (1964: 80), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 251), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404). D—AR, AZ.
- Fuscoporia laevigata*** (Fr.) G. Cunn. – *Phellinus laevigatus* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin; *Poria laevigata* (Fr.) P. Karst. – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 409), Martirosyan (1964: 85), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 260), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 417), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 30), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS. However, Parmasto (2007) has not seen any specimen of this species collected in the Caucasus region.
- Fuscoporia senex*** (Nees & Mont.) Ghobad-Nejhad – L—Hallenberg (1981: 498 as cf. *Phellinus johnsonianus*), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 208). E—Azerbaijan: Astara, Lenkoran, on *Parrotia persica*, 15 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 16406, 16410 and 16494). D—AZ, IRN.
- Fuscoporia torulosa*** (Pers.) T. Wagner & M. Fisch. – *Fomes castaneae* Woron.; *F. torulosus* (Pers.) Lloyd; *Phellinus torulosus* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Woronow (1915: 116), Woronichin (1924: 297, 1927: 154, 156), Bondarzew (1953: 376), Martirosyan (1965: 132), Morochkovskaya (1968: 203), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 248), Popushoy (1971: 220), Kanygina (1972: 181), Saber (1972: 38, 1974: 25), Kotlaba (1975: 14), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 119), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Melia *et al.* (1987: 131, 132), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 469), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 209), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Fuscoporia viticola*** (Schwein.) Murrill – *Phellinus viticola* (Schwein.) Donk – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková

- (1982: 31), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236). D—GR, RUS.
- Ganoderma adpersum* (Schulzer) Donk – L—Saber (1972: 28, 1974: 25), Soleimani (1976: 77), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 35), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 180), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 355), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 322), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 466), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Moradali *et al.* (2007: 257). D—AZ, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Ganoderma applanatum* (Pers.) Pat. – *Fomes applanatus* (Pers.) Gillet; *F. stevenii* (Lév.) P. Karst.; *Polyporus applanatus* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1908: 46, 1915: 114, 115), Bondarzew (1912: 113, 1953: 426), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1927: 154), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Pilát (1942: 491), Flerov (1962: 117), Kanygina (1964: 40, 1972: 181), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 264), Saber (1972: 30), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 336), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 674, 1976: 7), Steyaert (1975: descr. no. 443), Akhundov (1979: 129), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 31), Altan *et al.* (1986: 31), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 85, 86, 145, 146, 171, 173, 199, 251, 369, 456), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 94), Demirel (1999: 407), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 180), Türkekul (2003: 315), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 355), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 322), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 466), Mukhamedshin (2005: 235), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Moradali *et al.* (2007: 255), Sesli (2007: 80). D—The whole area.
- Ganoderma australe* (Fr.) Pat. – *Fomes australis* (Fr.) Cooke, *Ganoderma applanatum* f. *australe* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Woronow (1915: 115), Bondarzew (1953: 430), Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 171), Saber (2002: 286), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- **Ganoderma carnosum* Pat. – E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 11 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12167. D—RUS.
- Ganoderma lucidum* (Curtis) P. Karst. – *Fomes lucidus* (Curtis) Cooke; *Polyporus lucidus* (Curtis) Fr. – L—Buhse (1860: 245), Woronow (1908: 46, 1915: 113), Bondarzew (1912: 113, 1953: 432), Woronichin (1915b: 115, 1927: 156), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Kanygina (1964: 40), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 266), Saber (1972: 32, 1987: 26), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 673, 1976: 8), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 85, 86, 134, 145, 146, 172, 173, 200, 456), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 94), Bondartseva (1998: 78), Demirel (1999: 407), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 180), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 355), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 322), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 466), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Moradali *et al.* (2007: 260), Sesli (2007: 80). D—The whole area.
- Ganoderma pfeifferi* Bres. – L—Bondarzew (1953: 431), Bondartseva (1998: 80). D—RUS.
- Ganoderma resinaceum* Boud. – *Fomes resinaceum* (Boud.) Sacc.; *Ganoderma applanatum* subsp. *resinaceum* (Boud.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Woronow (1915: 114), Pilát (1942: 485), Bondarzew (1953: 434), Saber (1972: 33, 1987: 26), Steyaert (1980: 174), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 48), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Bondartseva (1998: 80), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 466), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Moradali *et al.* (2007: 262), Solak *et al.* (2007: 82). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Ganoderma tsugae* Murrill – L—Saber & Minassian (2000: 379), Moradali *et al.* (2007: 264). D—IRN.
- Gelatoporia pannocincta* (Romell) Niemelä – *Ceriporiopsis pannocincta* (Romell) Gilb. & Ryvarden; *Gloeoporus bourdotii* (Pilát) Bondartsev & Singer; *G. pannocinctus* (Romell) J. Erikss. – L—Bondarzew (1953: 257), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 194), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fagus* or *Carpinus*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22576. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Gloeophyllum abietinum* (Bull.) P. Karst. – *Lenzites abietina* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 151, 1905: 321), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 124), Woronichin (1927: 160), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 581), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 322), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Bondartseva (1998: 207), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Solak *et al.* (2007: 84). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22574. D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Gloeophyllum odoratum* (Wulfen) Imazeki – *Anisomyces odoratus* (Wulfen) Pilát; *Osmoporus odoratus* (Wulfen) Singer; *Trametes odorata* (Wulfen) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 122), Woronichin (1927: 159), Singer (1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 280), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Melia *et al.* (1987: 34), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Sesli (2007: 80). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, in *Taxus-Buxus* forest, on litter, 20 Jul 2005, Shiryayev (SVER 58021). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Gloeophyllum protractum* (Fr.) Imazeki – *Anisomyces caucasicus* (Bres.) Bondartsev; *Osmoporus protractum* (Fr.) Bondartsev; *Trametes odorata* var. *caucasica* Bres.; *T. protracta* Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 122), Woronichin (1927: 159), Nikolajeva (1938: 398), Bondarzew (1953: 282, 1959: 454), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Melia

- et al.* (1987: 19), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22564. D—GR, RUS.
- Gloeophyllum sepiarium*** (Wulfen) P. Karst. [incl. *G. sepiarium* var. *fagi* Nik.] – *Lenzites sepiaria* (Wulfen) Fr. [incl. var. *fagi* Nikol.] – L—Hollós (1902: 151, 1905: 321), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 124), Woronichin (1927: 160), Singer (1930: 78), Nikolajeva (1938: 425), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 579, 581), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Saber (2002: 286), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 472), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 148, 202). D—The whole area.
- Gloeophyllum trabeum*** (Pers.) Murrill – *Coriopsis trabea* (Pers.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Lenzites trabea* (Pers.) Fr.; *Trametes trabea* (Pers.) Bres. – L—Hollós (1902: 151, 1905: 321), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 123), Singer (1930: 79), Nikolajeva (1938: 399), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 533; 1959: 451), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Kanygina (1964: 42), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 322), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Bondartseva (1998: 214), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Asef (2008, pers. comm.). E—Iran: Gilan, Fuman, on a fallen branch, May 2008, Hallenberg 16056. Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22597. D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Gloeoporus dichrous*** (Fr.) Bres. – *Polyporus dichrous* Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 119), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 255), Kanygina (1964: 39), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Bondartseva (1998: 217), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Gloeoporus taxicola*** (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvarde – *Ceriporia taxicola* (Pers.) Komarova; *Meruliopsis taxicola* (Pers.) Bondartsev – L—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 329), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 417), Simonyan (1981: 150), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Gloeoporus tschulymicus*** (Pilát) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 195). D—AR.
- Grifola frondosa*** (Dicks.) Gray – *Polypilus frondosus* (Dicks.) P. Karst. [incl. var. *intybaceus* (Fr.) Bondartsev]; *Polyporus frondosus* (Dicks.) Fr.; *P. intybaceus* Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 117), Woronichin (1927: 157), Bondarzew (1953: 603, 605), Kanygina (1964: 42), Khabiri (1968: 137), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 10), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Melia *et al.* (1987: 74, 186, 203), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83), Bondartseva (1998: 49), Nikolayev (1999: 96, 2001: 99), Türkekül (2003: 315), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 474), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Haplophilus aurantiacus*** (Rostk.) Bondartsev & Singer – *H. salmonicolor* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Pouzar – L—Bondarzew (1953: 269), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 190), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96). D—AR, RUS.
- Haplophilus croceus*** (Pers.) Donk – *H. subtestaceus* (Bres.) Bondartsev; *Polyporus croceus* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 118), Solovjev (1932: 119), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 263, 1963: 114), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 193), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Melia *et al.* (1987: 134), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Nanagulyan & Senn-Irlet (2002: 2), Nanagulyan (2006: 2), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Haplophilus rutilans*** (Pers.) P. Karst. – *H. nidulans* (Fr.) P. Karst.; *Polyporus rutilans* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 261), Kanygina (1964: 39), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 191), Akhundov (1979: 130), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Simonyan (1981: 150), Melia *et al.* (1987: 147), Saber (2000: 374), Nikolayev (2001: 101). D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Haploporus odoratus*** (Sommerf.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Nanagulyan & Senn-Irlet (2002: 2), Nanagulyan (2006: 2). D—AR.
- Haploporus tuberculatus*** (Fr.) Niemelä & Y.C. Dai – *Coriolellus colliculosus* (Pers.) Bondartsev; *Pachykytospora tuberculosa* (DC.) Kotl. & Pouzar – L—Bondarzew (1953: 516), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 430), Bondartseva (1998: 282), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Heterobasidium abietinum*** Niemelä & Korhonen – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 37 as *Fomes annosus*), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 472 as *H. annosus* on fir), Doğan & Lehtijärvi *et al.* (2007: 388), Sesli (2007: “14”). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22615; Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Guzeripl', on roots of *A. nordmanniana*, 15 Sep 2003, Shiryaev (SVER 58300). D—RUS, TUR.
- Heterobasidium annosum*** (Fr.) Bref. s. lat. – *Fomes annosus* (Fr.) Cooke; *Fomitopsis annosa* (Fr.) P. Karst.; *Ungulina annosa* (Fr.) Pat. – L—Woronow (1915: 116), Singer (1930: 79), Bondarzew (1953: 302), Khabiri (1968: 138), Fallahyan (1973: 214), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 493), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 16, 27), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Demirel (1999: 407), Larsson (2001: 133), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Larsson & Larsson (2003: 1041), Larsson *et al.* (2004: 986), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 472), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 28). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR. However, no voucher or recent specimen was found by the first author in Iran.
- Heterobasidium annosum*** (Fr.) Bref. s. str. – L—Doğan & Lehtijärvi *et al.* (2007: 388). D—TUR.
- Inocutis dryophila*** (Berk.) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Inonotus dryophilus* (Berk.) Murrill; *Polyporus corruscans* Fr. –

- L—Woronow (1915: 119), Bondarzew (1953: 333), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 231), Kanygina (1972: 181, 1986: 46), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 104), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 65), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 149), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Inocutis levis* (P. Karst.) Y.C. Dai – *Inonotus pseudohispidus* Kravtzev – L—Hallenberg (1981: 498), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 468). D—IRN.
- Inocutis rheades* (Pers.) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Inonotus rheades* (Pers.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Kanygina (1964: 40), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 673), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 468). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Inocutis tamaricis* (Pat.) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Inonotus tamaricis* (Pat.) Maire – L—Bondarzew (1953: 336), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 104), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 76), Kanygina (1986: 47), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 469). D—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Inonotus andersonii* (Ellis & Everh.) Černý – L—Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 239), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 61), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129). D—AR.
- Inonotus cuticularis* (Bull.) P. Karst. – *Polyporus cuticularis* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 119), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 337), Kanygina (1964: 39), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 233), Kanygina (1972: 181), Saber (1972: 35, 1987: 27), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 8), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 62), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 95, 149, 186), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 471). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Inonotus dryadeus* (Pers.) Murrill – *Polyporus dryadeus* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Buhse (1860: 245), Woronow (1915: 119), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Solovjev (1932: 120), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Pilát (1942: 555), Vakin & Shtraukh (1950: 205), Bondarzew (1953: 321), Terevnikova-Babayana (1958: 26), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 229), Kanygina (1972: 181), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 8), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 64), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 186), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 79), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 471). D—The whole area.
- Inonotus hispidus* (Bull.) P. Karst. – *Polyporus hispidus* (Bull.) Fr.; *Xanthochrous hispidus* (Bull.) Pat. – L—Nevodovskiy (1914: 75), Woronow (1915: 119), Bondarzew (1953: 340), Mehdieva (1958: 13), Kanygina (1964: 39), Khabiri (1968: 138), Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 183), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 235), Fallahyan (1973: 214), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 673), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Simonyan (1981: 150), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 66), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 224, 369, 491), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Demirel (1999: 407), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 30), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 467), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 79), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 471). D—The whole area.
- Inonotus nidus-pici* Pilát – L—Hallenberg (1981: 497), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 472). D—IRN.
- Inonotus obliquus* (Pers.) Pilát [incl. *I. obliquus* f. *sterilis* (Vanin) Nikol.] – *Poria obliqua* (Ach. ex Pers.) P. Karst. – L—Bondarzew (1912: 118), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Khabiri (1968: 137), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 236), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 472). D—AR, GR, IRN.
- Inonotus plorans* (Pat.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 473). D—IRN.
- Irpex lacteus* (Fr.) Fr. [incl. *I. lacteus* f. *canescens* (Fr.) Bres.] – *Irpex canescens* Fr.; *I. sinuosus* Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915a: 14, 1915b: 16, 1927: 154), Woronow (1915: 111), Singer (1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 36), Petrak (1940: 427), Bondarzew (1953: 554), Nikolajeva (1953: 185, 187, 1961: 166), Kanygina (1964: 42), Martirosyan (1965: 133), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 310), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 24), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Melia *et al.* (1987: 89, 149, 220, 367), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Ischnoderma benzoinum* (Wahlenb.) P. Karst. – *Polyporus benzoinum* (Wahlenb.) Fr.; *Ungulina benzoina* (Wahlenb.) Singer – L—Woronow (1927: 157), Singer (1930: 82, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Bondartseva (1998: 235). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22582. D—GR, RUS.
- Ischnoderma resinosum* (Schr.) P. Karst. – L—Bondarzew (1953: 277), Kanygina (1964: 39), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 219), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AR, AZ, GR.
- Junghuhnia collabens* (Fr.) Ryvarden – *Chaetoporus rixosus* (P. Karst.) P. Karst. – L—Bondarzew (1953: 173), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Bondartseva (1998: 239). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on a trunk, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11346. D—RUS, TUR.

- **Junghubnia lacera* (P. Karst.) Niemelä & Kinnunen – E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Kalaleh, on a fallen branch, 11 May 2008, Hallenberg 16225. Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Fagus*, 8–10 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12126. D—IRN, RUS.
- Junghubnia nitida* (Pers.) Ryvarden – *Chaetoporus euporus* (P. Karst.) P. Karst., *Poria eupora* (P. Karst.) Cooke. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 170), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 184), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429), Saber (1987: 23), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jolfa, Missan, on *Quercus*, 29 Sep 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 333. Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fagus*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22603. Turkey: Trabzon, Uçarsu, on *Alnus*, 9 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11476. D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Laetiporus sulphureus* (Bull.) Murrill [incl. *L. sulphureus* f. *aporus* (Bourdot & Galzin) Bondartsev and f. *imbricatus* Domański] – *Polyporus caudicinus* (Schaeff.) J. Schröt.; *P. sulphureus* (Bull.) Fr. – L—Speshnev (1897: 217), Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronichin (1915b: 118, 1927: 157), Woronow (1915: 118), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 182, 185), Teterevnikova-Babayan (1958: 26), Kanygina (1964: 38, 1972: 181, 1986: 46), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Khabiri (1968: 137), Morochkovskaya (1968: 202), Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 183), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 216), Saber (1972: 35, 1987: 24, 2000: 374), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 8), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 34), Melia *et al.* (1987: 90, 96, 123, 126, 134, 150, 159, 178, 187, 203, 351, 439), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Nikolayev (2001: 99), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 472), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Sesli (2007: 80). D—The whole area.
- Lenzites betulinus* (L.) Fr. [incl. *L. betulinus* f. *flaccida* (Fr.) Bres., f. *variegata* (Fr.) Donk, and subsp. *variegata* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin] – *Daedalea betulina* (L.) Fr.; *Lenzites flaccida* (Bull.) Fr.; *L. variegata* (Fr.) Fr. – L—Buhse (1860: 244), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1915b: 116, 1927: 160), Woronow (1915: 123), Nikolajeva (1938: 427), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 574), Kanygina (1964: 42), Khabiri (1968: 138), Morochkovskaya (1968: 201), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 317, 318), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 9), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 37), Shainidze (1980: 212), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Saber (1987: 24), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 98), Sesli (1999: 97), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 30), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 472), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—The whole area.
- Lenzites warnieri* Durieu & Mont. – *L. reichardtii* Schulzer – L—Bondarzew (1912: 117, 1953: 577), Woronow (1915: 124), Woronichin (1927: 160), Nikolajeva (1938: 429), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 319), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 37), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Saber (1987: 24), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 99), Bondartseva (1998: 246), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Leptoporus mollis* (Pers.) Quél. – *L. mollis* (Pers.) Quél.; *Tyromyces erubescens* (Fr.) Donk; *T. mollis* (Pers.) Kotl. & Pouzar – L—Bondarzew (1953: 208), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Bondartseva (1998: 247), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS.
- Melanoporia nigra* (Berk.) Murrill – *Nigroporus niger* (Berk.) Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 494). D—IRN.
- Mensularia hastifera* (Pouzar) T. Wagner & M. Fisch. – *Inonotus hastifer* Pouzar – L—Ryvarden (2005: 68). D—RUS.
- Mensularia nodulosa* (Fr.) T. Wagner & M. Fisch. – *Inonotus nodulosus* (Fr.) P. Karst. [incl. var. *nodulosus* (Fr.) Pilát] – L—Bondarzew (1953: 326), Kanygina (1964: 39), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 69), Ryvarden (2005: 90), Ghobad-Nejhad & Kotiranta (2008: 473). D—AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Mensularia radiata* (Sowerby) Lázaro Ibiza – *Inonotus polymorphus* (Rostk.) Pilát; *I. radiatus* (Sowerby) P. Karst.; *Polyporus radiatus* (Sowerby) Fr.; *Polystictus radiatus* (Sowerby) Fr. – L—Woronichin (1916: 16), Nagorny (1930: 70), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 327), Kanygina (1964: 39), Akhundov (1979: 130), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 71), Melia *et al.* (1987: 494), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Meripilus giganteus* (Pers.) P. Karst. – *Polypilus giganteus* (Pers.) Donk; *Polyporus giganteus* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Woronichin (1927: 157), Singer (1930: 81), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 605), Kanygina (1964: 42), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Khabiri (1968: 137), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 332), Saber (1972: 36), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 103), Bondartseva (1998: 53), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 80). D—The whole area.
- Oligoporus hibernicus* (Berk. & Broome) Gilb. & Ryvarden – *Tyromyces hibernicus* (Berk. & Broome) Ryvarden – L—Hallenberg (1981: 496). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Baran-Kuh, on *Acer*, 30 Oct 2007, Ghobad-Nejhad 685. D—IRN.
- Oligoporus sericeomollis* (Romell) Bondartseva – *Aporpium buxi* (Bondartsev) Bondartsev & Singer ex Bondartsev; *Poria buxi* Bondartsev; *Tyromyces sericeomollis* (Romell) Bondartsev – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew

- (1940: 20, 1953: 161), Martirosyan (1963: 66), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 201), Simonyan (1981: 150), cf. Bondartseva (1998: 275). D—AR, RUS.
- Oligoporus simanii* (Pilát) Bernicchia – L—Renvall (2005:98). D—IRN.
- Onnia leporina* (Fr.) John – L—Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236). D—RUS.
- Onnia tomentosa* (Fr.) P. Karst. – *Onnia circinata* (Fr.) P. Karst.; *Polyporus tomentosus* Fr.; *Polystictus circinatus* (Fr.) Cooke; *P. tomentosus* (Fr.) Fr. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Melia *et al.* (1987: 33), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Lagonaki Plateau, on soil in *Fagus-Abies* forest, 18 Sep 2003, Shiryayev (SVER 58005). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Oxyporus pseudo-obducens* (Pilát) Bondartsev – L—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR. The more correct position of the species is possibly in the genus *Rigidoporus*.
- Perenniporia fraxinea* (Bull.) Ryvarden – *Fomes fraxineus* (Bull.) Cooke; *Ungulina fraxinea* (Bull.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Singer (1931: 517), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Melia *et al.* (1987: 85, 172), Saber (1987: 24), Bondartseva (1998: 287). E—Iran: Gilan, Lahijan, on hardwood stump, 1 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 839. D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Perenniporia medulla-panis* (Jacq.) Donk – *Fomitopsis unita* (Pers.) Bondartsev; *Poria medulla-panis* (Jacq.) Pers.; *P. medullaris* Gray – L—Woronow (1915: 112), Bondarzew (1953: 309), Ulianishchev (1958: 76), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 226), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 6), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Bondartseva (1998: 290), Spirin *et al.* (2005: 35), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 38). D—The whole area.
- Perenniporia narymica* (Pilát) Pouzar – *P. elongata* Domański – L—Hallenberg (1981: 494). D—IRN.
- Perenniporia subacida* (Peck) Donk – *Chaetoporus subacidus* (Peck) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404). D—AZ.
- Perenniporia tenuis* (Schwein.) Ryvarden – *Fomitopsis unita* var. *pulchella* Bourdot & Galzin; *Poria medulla-panis* var. *pulchella* Bourdot & Galzin; *P. pulchella* (Schwein.) Cooke – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 312), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 35). D—RUS.
- Phaeolus schweinitzii* (Fr.) Pat. – *Polyporus schweinitzii* Fr.; *P. sistotremoides* (Alb. & Schwein.) Murrill. – L—Woronow (1915: 117), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 316), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 228), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 32), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 38). D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Phellinidium ferrugineofuscum* (P. Karst.) Fiasson & Niemelä – *Phellinus ferrugineofuscum* (P. Karst.) Bourdot & Galzin – L—Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1994: 485, on map). E—Russia: Karachayevo-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on *Picea orientalis*, 20 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 53147). D—RUS.
- Phellinus alni* (Bondartsev) Parmasto – *Ph. igniarius* var. *alni* (Bondartsev) Niemelä; *Ph. igniarius* f. *alni* (Bondartsev) Cetto – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Kanygina (1986: 47), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR.
- Phellinus baumii* Pilát s. lat. – L—Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 210). D—IRN.
- Phellinus chrysoloma* (Fr.) Donk – *Ph. pini* var. *abietis* (P. Karst.) Pilát; *Trametes abietis* (P. Karst.) Sacc.; *T. pini* var. *abietis* P. Karst. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Pilát (1942: 521), Bondarzew (1953: 384), Selik (1973: 30), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Melia *et al.* (1987: 18), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: “5”). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Phellinus cinereus* (Niemelä) M. Fisch. (non Rick) – *Ph. igniarius* f. *betulae* Bondartsev; *Ph. igniarius* var. *cinereus* Niemelä – L—Gulmagarashvili (1975: 674), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Phellinus conchatus* (Pers.) Quél. [incl. *Ph. conchatus* f. *aceris* Bondartsev and f. *loniceriae* (Weimer) Bondarzew] – *Fomes salicinus* (Pers.) Gillet – L—Woronichin (1927: 156), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 368), Martirosyan (1964: 77), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 245, 246), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 417), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 88), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438, 439), Melia *et al.* (1987: 48), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Phellinus igniarius* (L.) Quél. s. lat. [incl. *Ph. igniarius* f. *salicis* Bondartsev] – *Fomes igniarius* (L.) Cooke; *Ochroporus igniarius* (L.) J. Schröt.; *Polyporus igniarius* Fr. – L—Speshnev (1895: 71), Hollós (1902: 149), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 115), Woronichin (1927: 156), Singer (1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 349), Kanygina (1964: 40, 1972: 181, 1986: 46), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 241, 242), Saber (1974: 25, 1987: 28), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 9), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 35), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 29), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Melia *et al.* (1987: 74, 85, 145, 172, 183, 431), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Demirel & Uzun (2002: 292), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 180), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 468), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 40), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 212),

- Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 79). D—The whole area.
- Pbellinus lundellii* Niemelä – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 30). D—RUS.
- Pbellinus lonicerinus* (Bondartsev) Bondartsev & Singer – *Ph. linteus* sensu M. Bondartseva (1986; vide Parmasto & Parmasto 2001: 59) – L—Martirosyan (1964: 78), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 247), Gulmagarashvili (1974: 418, 1975: 674), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR.
- Pbellinus nigricans* (Fr.) P. Karst. – *Fomes nigricans* (Fr.) Gillet; *Polyporus nigricans* Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 115), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 30), Melia *et al.* (1987: 173, 432), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 30), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 355), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 323), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 468), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41). D—RUS, TUR.
- Pbellinus nigrolimitatus* (Romell) Bourdot & Galzin [incl. *Ph. nigrolimitatus* f. *spongiosus* Murashk.] – L—Bondarzew (1953: 374, 376), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 110), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Pbellinus pini* (Brot.) Bondartsev & Singer [incl. *Ph. pini* var. *typicus* Pilát] – *Trametes pini* (Brot.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 122), Woronichin (1927: 159), Bondarzew (1953: 379), Martirosyan (1964: 79), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 249, 251), Simonyan (1981: 150), Altan *et al.* (1986: 31), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Melia *et al.* (1987: 31, 34), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 38). D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Pbellinus pouzarii* Kotl. – L—Kotlaba (1968: 27), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 113). D—RUS.
- Pbellinus rhamnii* (Bondartseva) H. Jahn – L—Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 115), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Parmasto (2007: 49). D—RUS.
- Pbellinus rimosus* (Berk.) Pilát – L—Bondarzew (1953: 397), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 116), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Pbellinus tremulae* (Bondartsev) Bondartsev & Borisov – L—Bondarzew (1953: 356), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 9), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 30), Kanygina (1986: 46), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Mukhamedshin (2005: 235), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Pbellinus tuberculosus* (Baumg.) Niemelä – *Fomes fulvus* R. Hartig non (Scop.) Gillet; *Pbellinus pomaceus* (Pers.) Maire – L—Woronow (1915: 115, 1916: 257), Woronichin (1927: 156), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 358), Morochkovskaya (1968: 202), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 243), Kanygina (1972: 181), Saber (1972: 36), Akhundov (1979: 130), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 104), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Simonyan (1981: 150), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439), Melia *et al.* (1987: 335), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 30), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 469), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 212), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Pbellinus vorax* (Harkn.) Černý – L—Sesli (1999: 96, 2007: 79), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 469), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41). D—TUR.
- Pbellinus weirii* (Murrill) Gilb. – *Inonotus weirii* (Murrill) Kotl. & Pouzar – L—Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236). D—RUS.
- Phylloporia ampelina* (Bondartsev & Singer) Bondartseva – *Pbellinus ampelinus* Bondartsev & Singer – L—Bondarzew (1953: 400), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 674), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 46), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—GR.
- Phylloporia ephedrae* (Woron.) Parmasto – *Fomes ephedrae* Woron.; *F. ribis* f. *jasmini* Quél.; *Pbellinus ribis* f. *ephedrae-nebrodensis* Bourdot & Galzin; *Ph. ribis* f. *jasmini* (Quél.) Pilát – L—Woronow (1915: 116), Woronichin (1924: 299, 300; 1927: 155), Bondarzew (1953: 393, 394), Parmasto & Parmasto (1983: 94), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 48), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Melia *et al.* (1987: 43, 44), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Phylloporia ribis* (Schumach.) Ryvarden – *Fomes ribis* (Schumach.) Fr., *Pbellinus ribis* (Schumach.) Quél. [incl. f. *euonymi* (Kalchbr.) Pilát] – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 391, 393), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 252), Popushoy (1971: 220), Saber (1974: 23), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 105), Hallenberg (1981: 498), Parmasto & Parmasto (1983: 94), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 49), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 439, 440), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 213), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Phylloporia spathulata* (Hook.) Ryvarden – *Coltricia spathulata* (Hooker) Murrill – L—Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 34), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Ghobad-Nejhad & Dai (2007: 214). D—IRN.
- Physisporinus sanguinolentus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Pilát – *Podoporia sanguinolenta* (Alb. & Schwein.) Höhn.; *Poria sanguinolenta* (Alb. & Schwein.) Cooke; *Rigidoporus sanguinolentus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Donk – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 132), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 173), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 36), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–12 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11570. D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Physisporinus vitreus* (Pers.) P. Karst. – *Podoporia vitrea* (Pers.) Donk; *Poria vitrea* Pers. – L—Woronow (1915: 112), Pilát (1939: 252), Bondarzew (1953: 134), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 174), Melia *et al.* (1987: 189), Bondartseva (1998: 358), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.

- Piptoporus betulinus* (Bull.) P. Karst. – *Placoderma betulinum* (Bull.) Fr.; *Polyporus betulinus* (Bull.) Fr.; *Ungulina betulina* (Bull.) Pat. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17), Nevodovskiy (1914: 8), Woronow (1915: 119), Woronichin (1927: 157), Singer (1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 271), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 218), Fallahyan (1973: 214), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 674, 1976: 10), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Melia *et al.* (1987: 115, 439), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 151, 202). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Piptoporus quercinus* (Schrud.) P. Karst. – *Buglossoporus pulvinus* (Pers.) Donk; *Polyporus quercinus* (Schrud.) Fr. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 274), Melia *et al.* (1987: 158), Bondartseva (1998: 95), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403). D—AZ, GR, RUS.
- Piptoporus soloniensis* (Dubois) Pilát – L—Bondarzew (1953: 276), Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1994: 548, on map), Bondartseva (1998: 96). D—GR, RUS.
- Podofomes corrugis* (Fr.) Pouzar – *Pelloporus corrugis* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Bondarzew (1953: 283), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83). D—RUS.
- Podofomes trogii* (Fr.) Pouzar – *Ischnoderma trogii* (Fr.) Teixeira – L—Bondarzew (1953: 284), Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1994: 552), Bondartseva (1998: 237), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 40). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22501. D—GR, RUS, TUR.
- Polyporus alveolaris* (DC.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Bondarzew (1953: 445), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Bondartseva (1998: 99). D—AR, GR, RUS.
- Polyporus arcularius* (Batsch) Fr. – *Leucoporus arcularius* (Batsch) Quél.; *Polyporus agariceus* Berk.; *P. anisoporus* Delastre & Mont. – L—Woronow (1915: 116), Woronichin (1927: 157), Singer (1930: 82, 1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 467, 472), Mehdieva (1958: 13), Kanygina (1964: 40), Martirosyan (1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 276, 280), Popushoy (1971: 225), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 11), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 38), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Altan *et al.* (1986: 31), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 101), Demirel (1999: 407), Saber (2000: 374, as *Polyporus brumalis*), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Saber (2002: 286), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 473), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Polyporus badius* (Pers.) Schwein. – *Polyporellus picipes* (Fr.) P. Karst.; *Polyporus picipes* Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 117), Woronichin (1927: 157), Pilát (1937: 101), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 453), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 273), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 11), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Saber (1987: 24), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Demirel (1999: 407), Demirel & Uzun (2002: 292), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 474), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 80). D—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Polyporus brumalis* (Pers.) Fr. [incl. *P. brumalis* f. *subarcularius* Donk] – *P. subarcularius* (Donk) Bondartsev – L—Siemaszko (1923: 27), Bondarzew (1953: 460, 470), Kanygina (1964: 40), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 276, 278), Popushoy (1971: 225), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 11), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Türkekul (2003: 315), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 474), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Polyporus ciliatus* Fr. [incl. *P. ciliatus* f. *vernalis* Weinm.] – *P. brumalis* auct. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 116), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Polyporus guianensis* Mont. – L—Sesli & Denchev (2009: 41). D—TUR.
- Polyporus lepideus* Fr. – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34). D—RUS.
- Polyporus melanopus* (Pers.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 117), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Martirosyan (1971: 275), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 35), Melik-Khachatryan & Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 36), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Polyporus meridionalis* (A. David) H. Jahn – L—Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 474). D—TUR.
- Polyporus rhizophilus* (Pat.) Sacc. – L—Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 35), Bondartseva (1998: 107). D—RUS.
- Polyporus squamosus* (Huds.) Fr. – *Melanopus squamosus* (Huds.) Pat. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 117), Woronichin (1927: 157), Singer (1930: 81, 1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 437), Mehdieva (1958: 13), Kanygina (1964: 40), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Khabiri (1968: 137), Morochkovskaya (1968: 201), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 269), Saber (1972: 38, 2000: 374), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 11), Akhundov (1979: 129), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 35), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 36), Melia *et al.* (1987: 74, 96, 159, 187, 224), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Demirel & Uzun (2002: 292), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 182), Türkekul (2003: 315), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 474), Mukhamedshin

- (2005: 235), Shagapsoev & Krapivina (2005: 333), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 80). **D**—The whole area.
- Polyporus tuberaster*** (Jacq.) Fr. — *P. coronatus* Rostk.; *P. floccipes* Rostk.; *P. forquignonii* Quél.; *P. lentus* Berk. — **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 442, 444), Kanygina (1964: 40), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 270), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 36), Saber (1987: 24), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Bondartseva (1998: 110), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403, 405), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 41). **D**—The whole area.
- ****Polyporus udus*** Jungh. — **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Fagus*, 17 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22572. **D**—**RUS**. Earlier known only from E Asia.
- Polyporus umbellatus*** (Pers.) Fr. — *Dendropolyporus umbellatus* (Pers.) Jülich; *Grifola umbellata* (Pers.) Pilát; *Polypilus umbellatus* (Pers.) P. Karst. — **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 607), Saber (1987: 25), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83), Bondartseva (1998: 113), Sesli (1999: 97, 2007: 80), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 471). **D**—**IRN, RUS, TUR**.
- Polyporus varius*** (Pers.) Fr. [incl. *P. varius* var. *nummularius* f. *petalodes* (Fr.) Domański, Orlos & Skirg.] — *Melanopus nummularius* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin; *Polyporus elegans* Fr.; *P. leptodes* Rostk.; *P. leptcephalus* (Jacq.) Fr.; *P. nummularius* Fr. — **L**—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Rostrup (1908: 17), Woronow (1915: 116, 117), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Woronichin (1927: 157), Singer (1930: 81, 1931: 518), Vasil'eva (1939: 39, 40, 41), Bondarzew (1953: 447, 449, 451, 452), Kanygina (1964: 40), Martirosyan (1965: 133), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 272, 273), Saber (1974: 25), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 10), Akhundov (1979: 129), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 35), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 441), Vaasma *et al.* (1986: 37), Melia *et al.* (1987: 187, 188), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 102), Nikolayev (2001: 100), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Badalyan (2003: 39), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 182), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). **D**—The whole area.
- Porotheleum fimbriatum*** (Pers.) Fr. — *Stromatoscypha fimbriata* (Pers.) Donk — **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 616), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 336), Hallenberg (1981: 499), Bondartseva & Parmasto (1986: 177), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 94), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404). **E**—Azerbaijan: Zakataly, Zakataly Nature Reserve, on *Fagus orientalis*, 4 Aug 1974, I. Parmasto (TAA 90354); 9 Aug 1974, Murdvee (TAA 68410). Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11336. **D**—The whole area.
- Porpomyces mucidus*** (Pers.) Jülich — *Ceriporiopsis mucida* (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvarden; *Poria mucida* Pers. — **L**—Woronow (1915: 112), Woronichin (1916: 16), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Melia *et al.* (1987: 96, 189), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Vaighan, on harwood twig, 2 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad; Qale-darasi, on *Carpinus*, 5 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 442. Russia: Krasnodar, Khosta, on *Taxus*, 9 Aug 1996, Hallenberg 12959. Turkey: Trabzon, Çilekli, on *Fagus*, 10 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11513. **D**—**GR, IRN, RUS, TUR**.
- Postia balsamea*** (Peck) Jülich — *Oligoporus balsameus* (Peck) Gilb. & Ryvarden; *Polyporus kymatodes* auct.; *Tyromyces kymatodes* Donk — **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 40 as *Polyporus kymatodes* Rostk.), Bondarzew (1953: 216), Martirosyan (1963: 70), Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 183), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 206), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 11), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Melia *et al.* (1987: 96, 187 as *Polyporus kymatodes*), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Bondartseva (1998: 257), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—**AR, AZ, GR, RUS**.
- Postia caesia*** (Schrad.) P. Karst. — *Oligoporus caesius* (Schrad.) Gilb. & Ryvarden; *Polyporus caesius* Schrad.; *Tyromyces caesius* (Schrad.) Murrill — **L**—Woronow (1915: 118), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 198), Martirosyan (1963: 72), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 209), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 37), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Adler, on a trunk of *Abies*, 20 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13210. **D**—**AR, GR, RUS, TUR**.
- Postia ceriflua*** (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Jülich — *Tyromyces revolutus* (Bres.) Bondartsev & Singer — **L**—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—**GR**.
- Postia floriformis*** (Quél.) Jülich — *Tyromyces floriformis* (Quél.) Bondartsev & Singer — **L**—Martirosyan (1963: 71), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 207), Simonyan (1981: 150). **D**—**AR**.
- Postia fragilis*** (Fr.) Jülich — *Polyporus fragilis* Fr.; *P. weinmannii* Fr.; *Tyromyces fragilis* (Fr.) Donk — **L**—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 317), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronow (1915: 118, 119), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Melia *et al.* (1987: 32), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—**GR, RUS**.
- Postia lactea*** (Fr.) P. Karst. — *Leptoporus lacteus* (Fr.) Pat.; *Polyporus lacteus* Fr.; *Tyromyces lacteus* (Fr.) Murrill — **L**—Woronichin (1915b: 115), Woronow (1915: 118), Singer (1931: 518), Bondarzew (1953: 190), Martirosyan (1963: 69), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 205), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Melia *et al.* (1987: 186). **D**—**AR, GR, IRN, RUS**.
- Postia stiptica*** (Pers.) Jülich — *Oligoporus stipticus* (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvarden; *Tyromyces albidus* (Schaeff.) Donk; *T. stipticus* (Pers.) Kotl. & Pouzar — **L**—Bondarzew (1949: 92, 1953: 210), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 37), Sesli (2007: “7”). **D**—**GR, RUS, TUR**.
- Postia tephroleuca*** (Fr.) Jülich — *Leptoporus tephroleucus* (Fr.) Quél.; *Oligoporus tephroleucus* (Fr.) Gilb. & Ryvarden;

- Tyromyces tephroleucus* (Fr.) Donk – L—Singer (1930: 82), Bondarzew (1953: 193), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Sesli (1999: 97, 2007: “7”), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 475), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). D—AZ, GR, RUS, TUR.
- *Protomerulius caryae* (Schwein.) Ryvarden – *Aporpium caryae* (Schwein.) Teixeira & D.P. Rogers – L—Simonyan (1981: 150), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Baran-Kuh, on *Carpinus*, 30 Oct 2007, coll. Sohrabi (Ghobad-Nejhad 675). Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on wood, 15 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22557. D—AR, AZ, IRN, RUS.
- Pycnoporellus alboluteus* (Ellis & Everh.) Kotl. & Pouzar – L—Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1994: 591, on map), Bondartseva (1998: 86). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on *Abies*, 9 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12104. D—RUS. According to Bondartseva (1998), found also in the Caucasus beyond Russian border.
- Pycnoporellus fulgens* (Fr.) Donk – *Hapalopilus fibrillosus* (P. Karst.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Polyporus fibrillosus* P. Karst. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 265), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22516. D—GR, RUS.
- Pycnoporus cinnabarinus* (Jacq.) P. Karst. – *Polyporus cinnabarinus* (Jacq.) Fr.; *Trametes cinnabarina* (Jacq.) Fr. – L—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 122), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1927: 158), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Singer (1930: 79, 1931: 516), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 474), Kanygina (1964: 40), Bagdasarova (1965: 69), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 283), Saber (1972: 41), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 10), Shainidze (1980: 211), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 36), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 442), Melia *et al.* (1987: 108, 117, 191), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 99), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 74), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—The whole area.
- Pyrofomes demidoffii* (Lév.) Kotl. & Pouzar – *Phellinus demidoffii* (Lév.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Bondarzew (1953: 398), Martirosyan (1964: 81, 1965: 131), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 254), Gulmagarashvili (1975: 673), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 106), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Kanygina (1986: 47), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 92), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: Ardabil, S Khalkhal, 15 km to Hashhtjin, on *Juniperus excelsa*, 6 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 1042. Russia: Krasnodar, Tuapse, on *Cupressus* sp., 11 Nov 2003, Shiryayev (SVER 58003). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Rhodonina placenta* (Fr.) Niemelä, K.H. Larsson & Schigel – *Tyromyces placenta* (Fr.) Ryvarden – L—Doğan *et al.* (2005: 476). E—Russia: Krasnodar, Caucasus Nature Reserve, Umpyr', on *Abies nordmanniana*, 14 Aug 1976, Puusepp (TAA 109240). D—RUS, TUR.
- Rigidoporus corticola* (Fr.) Pouzar – *Chaetoporus corticola* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer; *C. pearsonii* (Pilát) Bondartsev; *Oxyporus corticola* (Fr.) Parmasto, *Poria corticola* (Fr.) Sacc. – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 176, 180), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 187), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 429), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). D—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- *Rigidoporus crocatus* (Pat.) Ryvarden – *R. nigrescens* (Bres.) Donk – L—Saber (1987: 25), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236). E—Iran: Golestan, Gorgan, Baran-Kuh, on *Acer*, 30 Oct 2007, Ghobad-Nejhad 683. D—IRN, RUS.
- Rigidoporus latemarginatus* (E.J. Durand & Mont.) Pouzar – *Chaetoporus ambiguus* (Bres.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Oxyporus latemarginatus* (Durieu & Mont.) Donk; *Poria ambigua* Bres. – L—Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 178), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 188), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Bondartseva (1998: 352), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Nikolayev (2001: 101). D—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- *Rigidoporus obducens* (Pers.) Pouzar – *Oxyporus obducens* (Pers.) Donk; *Poria obducens* (Pers.) Cooke – L—Woronow (1915: 113), Siemaszko (1923: 27), Bondarzew (1953: 547), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 97), Bondartseva (1998: 353), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). E—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jolfa, Daran, on *Ulmus*, 25 Apr 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 755; Golestan, Gorgan, Baran-Kuh, on *Acer*, 30 Oct 2007, Ghobad-Nejhad 707. D—GR, IRN, RUS.
- Rigidoporus populinus* (Schumach.) Pouzar – *Fomes populinus* (Schumach.) Cooke; *Oxyporus populinus* (Schumach.) Donk; *Polyporus populinus* (Schumach.) Fr. – L—Woronow (1915: 116), Vasil'eva (1939: 37), Bondarzew (1953: 544), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 9), Shainidze (1980: 212), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438), Melia *et al.* (1987: 59, 96, 187, 459), Bondartseva (1998: 356), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202), Solak *et al.* (2007: 143). D—GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Rigidoporus ravidus* (Fr.) Pouzar – *Oxyporus ravidus* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Bondarzew (1953: 550), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 308), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 438). D—AR, GR.
- Rigidoporus ulmarius* (Sowerby) Imazeki – *Fomes cytisinus* Berk.; *F. ulmarius* Fr.; *Fomitopsis cytisina* (Berk.) Bondartsev & Singer; *F. ulmaria* (Sowerby) Bondartsev & Singer – L—Woronow (1915: 114), Pilát (1940: 358), Bondarzew (1953: 297, 299), Kanygina (1964: 39, 1972: 181), Vasil'eva & Kameshko (1968: 183), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 225), Saber (1972: 25, 41, 1974: 26), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 7), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 38), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Nakhutsrishvili (1986:

- 433), Melia *et al.* (1987: 146, 199), Bondartseva (1998: 361), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 475), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—The whole area.
- Rigidoporus undatus* (Pers.) Donk – *Poria undata* (Pers.) Quél. – **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 41). **E**—Azerbaijan: Leriki, on hardwood in *Parrotia* forest, 9 Oct 1962, Parmasto (TAA 15876). **D**—AZ, RUS.
- Skeletocutis amorpha* (Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar – *Gloeoporus amorphus* (Fr.) Killerm.; *Polyporus amorphus* Fr. – **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 250), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—GR, RUS.
- **Skeletocutis carneogrisea* A. David – **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies nordmanniana*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22512. **D**—RUS.
- Skeletocutis nivea* (Jungh.) Jean Keller – *Incrustoporia nivea* (Jungh.) Ryvarden; *Tyromyces semipileatus* (Peck) Murrill [incl. f. *resupinatus* Bourdot & Galzin] – **L**—Bondarzew (1953: 213), Martirosyan (1963: 72), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 208), Hallenberg (1981: 494), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 34), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Kaleibar, Qaledarasi, on *Carpinus*, 5 Oct 2006, Ghobad-Nejhad 459. Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea* branch, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11275. **D**—The whole area.
- Skeletocutis odora* (Peck ex Sacc.) Ginns – *Incrustoporia tschulymica* (Pilát) Domański – **L**—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129). **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 18 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22626. **D**—AR, RUS.
- **Skeletocutis papyracea* A. David – **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Mostovskoy, Umpyr', on a fallen log of *Pinus*, 7 Sep 1991, Hallenberg 12015. **D**—RUS.
- **Skeletocutis stellae* (Pilát) Jean Keller – **E**—Russia: Karachayevo-Cherkessia, Teberda Nature Reserve, on *Pinus hamata*, 17 Sep 1968, Parmasto (TAA 016). **D**—RUS.
- Skeletocutis subincarnata* (Peck) Jean Keller s. lat. – *Incrustoporia subincarnata* (Peck) Domański – **L**—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Turkey: Trabzon, Maçka, on *Picea*, 2–4 Oct 1989, Hallenberg 11362. **D**—GR, TUR.
- Spongipellis delectans* (Peck) Murrill – **L**—Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1994: 643, on map). **D**—?RUS.
- Spongipellis fissilis* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Murrill – *Aurantiporus fissilis* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) H. Jahn ex Ryvarden; *Polyporus albosordescens* Romell; *Tyromyces fissilis* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Donk – **L**—Bondarzew (1953: 221), Kanygina (1964: 38), Popushoy (1971: 210), Hallenberg (1981: 492), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Bondartseva (1998: 337), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403, 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Spongipellis fractipes* (Berk. & Curt.) Kotl. & Pouzar – **L**—Kotlaba & Pouzar (1976: 190). **D**—GR.
- Spongipellis litschaueri* Lohweg – **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 245), Kanygina (1964: 38), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 402). **D**—AZ, RUS. Possibly a synonym of *S. spumeus* (Sowerby) Pat.
- Spongipellis pachyodon* (Pers.) Kotl. & Pouzar – **L**—Ryvarden & Gilbertson (1994: 644, on map), Asef (2006: 158). **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Apsheonsk, Pyatigorsk, on *Fagus orientalis*, 1 Oct 1966, Parmasto (TAA 18895). **D**—IRN, RUS.
- Spongipellis spumeus* (Sowerby) Pat. – *Leptoporus spumeus* (Sowerby) Pilát; *Polyporus spumeus* (Sowerby) Fr. – **L**—Woronichin (1915b: 115), Woronow (1915: 119, 1927: 157), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Singer (1931: 518), Pilát (1938: 238), Bondarzew (1953: 243), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 213), Popushoy (1971: 212), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 74), Bondartseva (1998: 319), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—AR, AZ, GR, RUS.
- Sporotrichum roseolum* Oudem. & Beij. – **L**—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—GR.
- Trametes gibbosa* (Pers.) Fr. – *Daedalea gibbosa* (Pers.) Pers., *Pseudotrametes gibbosa* (Pers.) Bondartsev & Singer [incl. f. *kalchbrenneri* (Fr.) Bondartsev] – **L**—Hollós (1902: 150, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Bondarzew (1912: 114, 1953: 521, 522), Woronow (1915: 121), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Woronichin (1927: 159), Singer (1931: 517), Nikolajeva (1938: 410), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Flerov (1962: 117), Kanygina (1964: 41), Khabiri (1968: 138), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 304), Saber (1972: 42, 1987: 25, 2002: 286), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 11), Akhundov (1979: 130), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Melia *et al.* (1987: 82, 192, 429, 496), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 98), Bondartseva (1998: 323), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 475), Mukhamedshin (2005: 235), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli (2007: 81). **D**—The whole area.
- Trametes hirsuta* (Wulfen) Pilát – *Coriolus hirsutus* (Wulfen) Pat. [incl. f. *fuscomarginatus* Bres. and f. *resupinatus* Killerm.]; *Polyporus hirsutus* (Wulfen) Fr.; *Polystictus hirsutus* (Wulfen) Fr. – **L**—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 17), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1915b: 115, 1927: 157), Woronow (1915: 121), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 39), Bondarzew (1953: 487), Mehdiava (1958: 12), Kanygina (1964: 41), Morochkovskaya (1968: 202), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 289, 290), Saber (1972: 42, 1987: 26, 2000: 374), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 337), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 6), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 38), Akhundov (1979: 129), Shainidze (1980: 211), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 36), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 115, 140, 166, 188, 224, 439), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73),

- Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 475), Mukhamedshin (2005: 233), Kummer (2007: 145, 202), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—The whole area.
- Trametes ljubarskii* Pilát – *Haploporus ljubarskii* (Pilát) Bondartsev & Singer ex Bondartsev – **L**—cf. Schwartzman (1964: 570), Hallenberg (1981: 496). **D**—IRN, ?RUS.
- Trametes ochracea* (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvarden – *Coriolus zonatus* (Nees) Quél. [incl. f. *hirsutum transiens* Bres.]; *Polyporus zonatus* Nees; *Polystictus zonatus* (Nees) Fr.; *Trametes zonatella* Ryvarden – **L**—Buhse (1860: 245), Woronow (1915: 121), Woronichin (1916: 17, 1927: 158), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Bondarzew (1953: 485), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Flerov (1962: 117), Kanygina (1964: 41), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 288, 289), Frolov *et al.* (1979: 105), Shainidze (1980: 212), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 37), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 188), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 98), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Saber (2002: 285, as *Trichaptum abietinum*), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Iran: Gilan, Masal, Tiaskuh, on hardwood, 3 May 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 926. **D**—AR, AZ, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Trametes pubescens* (Schumach.) Pilát – *Coriolus pubescens* (Schumach.) Quél.; *Polyporus pubescens* (Schumach.) Fr. – **L**—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 119), Vasil'eva (1939: 40), Bondarzew (1953: 483), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Kanygina (1964: 41), Khabiri (1968: 136), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 287), Saber (1972: 44, 1987: 26, 2000: 374), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 6), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 37), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 100), Kazemzade *et al.* (1990: 103), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Demirel (1999: 407), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 31), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 476), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—The whole area.
- Trametes suaveolens* (L.) Fr. – **L**—Hollós (1902: 150, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 122), Bondarzew (1953: 519), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 302), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Bondartseva (1998: 327), Uzun *et al.* (2006: 41), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—AR, GR, IRN, RUS, TUR.
- Trametes velutina* (Pers.) G. Cunn. – *Coriolus velutinus* (Pers.) Pat.; *Polyporus velutinus* Pers.; *Polystictus velutinus* (Pers.) Sacc. – **L**—Weinmann (1836: 322), Rabenhorst (1871: 23), Woronow (1915: 121), Woronichin (1927: 158), Khabiri (1968: 136), Soleimani (1976: 77), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **D**—GR, IRN.
- Trametes versicolor* (L.) Lloyd – *Coriolus versicolor* (L.) Quél. [incl. f. *cyaneus* Velen., f. *fuscatus* Fr., and var. *cyaneus* Velen.]; *Polyporus versicolor* (L.) Fr. [incl. var. *fuscatus* (Fr.) Fr.]; *Polystictus versicolor* (L.) Fr. – **L**—Buhse (1860: 245), Rabenhorst (1871: 23), Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Bondarzew (1912: 114, 1953: 480), Woronichin (1915a: 15, 1916: 16, 1927: 152, 158), Woronow (1915: 120), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 41), Mehdieva (1958: 12), Flerov (1962: 117), Kanygina (1964: 41), Bagdasarova (1965: 68), Khabiri (1968: 136), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 286, 287), Saber (1972: 45, 1974: 26, 2000: 374, 2002: 286), Watling & Sweeney (1974: 337), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 6), Niemelä & Uotila (1977: 38), Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 79), Shainidze (1980: 211), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Simonyan (1981: 150), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 37), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Melia *et al.* (1987: 140, 166, 188, 440, 494), Parmasto & Parmasto (1989: 73), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 98, 1999: 129), Demirel (1999: 407), Sesli (1999: 97, 2007: 81), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73), Demirel *et al.* (2003: 30), Pekşen & Karaca (2003: 181), Türkekul (2003: 315), Afyon & Yağiz (2004: 356), Afyon *et al.* (2005: 324), Doğan *et al.* (2005: 476), Shagapsoev & Krapivina (2005: 333), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). **D**—The whole area.
- Trametopsis cervina* (Schwein.) Tomšovský – *Coriolus cervinus* (Schwein.) Bondartsev [incl. f. *resupinatus* Bres.]; *Trametes cervina* (Schwein.) Bres. – **L**—Nikolajeva (1938: 416), Vasil'eva (1939: 42), Bondarzew (1953: 493, 495), Kanygina (1964: 41), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 292), Popushoy (1971: 228), Hallenberg (1981: 495), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97), Bondartseva (1998: 322), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). **E**—Iran: E Azerbaijan, Jolfa, Ersi, on *Populus*, 25 Apr 2008, Ghobad-Nejhad 760. **D**—The whole area.
- Trichaptum abietinum* (Dicks.) Ryvarden – *Coriolus abietinus* (Dicks.) Quél.; *Hirschioporus abietinus* (Pers.) Donk; *Polyporus abietinus* (Dicks.) Fr.; *Polystictus abietinus* (Dicks.) Fr. – **L**—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 120, 121, 1915: 121), Siemaszko (1923: 28), Woronichin (1927: 157), Singer (1930: 80, 1931: 517), Vasil'eva (1939: 38), Bondarzew (1953: 558), Soleimani (1976: 77), Klán & Kotilová-Kubičková (1982: 32), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Melia *et al.* (1987: 14, 18, 32), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 99), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). **E**—Russia: Krasnodar, Adygeya, on *Abies*, 14 Sep 2003, Kotiranta 22508. **D**—AR, GR, IRN, RUS.
- Trichaptum biforme* (Fr.) Ryvarden – *Hirschioporus pargamenum* (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer; *Polystictus pargamenum* (Fr.) Cooke; *Trichaptum pargamenum* (Fr.) G. Cunn. – **L**—Bondarzew (1912: 114, 1953: 561), Woronow (1915: 120), Woronichin (1927: 158), Kanygina (1964: 42), Bagdasarova (1965: 69), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 312), Saber (1972: 33, 1974: 25), Gulmagarashvili (1976: 8), Niemelä &

- Uotila (1977: 37), Hallenberg (1981: 496), Simonyan (1981: 150), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 435), Melia *et al.* (1987: 96, 103, 115, 188), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 100), Hallenberg & Küffer (2001: 432), Nikolayev (2001: 101), Türkukul (2003: 315), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 145, 202). **D**—The whole area.
- Trichaptum fuscoviolaceum* (Ehrenb.) Ryvar den – *Hirschioporus fuscoviolaceus* (Ehrenb.) Donk; *Irpex fuscoviolaceus* (Ehrenb.) Fr. – **L**—Woronichin (1927: 154), Singer (1930: 77), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Melia *et al.* (1987: 28), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Kummer (2007: 202). **D**—GR, RUS.
- Trichaptum subchartaceum* (Murrill) Ryvar den – **L**—Bondartseva (1998: 334). **D**—GR.
- Tyromyces chioneus* (Fr.) P. Kars. – *Polyporus albellus* Peck; *P. chioneus* Fr.; *Tyromyces albellus* (Peck) Bondartsev & Singer – **L**—Vasil'eva (1939: 38, 39), Martirosyan (1963: 67), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 202), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007), Sesli & Denchev (2009: 48). **D**—AR, GR, RUS, TUR.
- Tyromyces kmetii* (Bres.) Bondartsev & Singer – *Polyporus kmetii* Bres. – **L**—Singer (1930: 82), Martirosyan (1963: 68, 1965: 131), Kotlaba & Pouzar (1965: 75), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 203), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 96), Bondartseva (1998: 338). **D**—AR, GR, RUS.
- Tyromyces wynnei* (Berk. & Broome) Donk – Sesli & Denchev (2009: 48). **E**—Turkey: Trabzon, on branch of *Fagus*, 26 Sep 1996, Hallenberg 13254. **D**—TUR.
- Records with uncertain affinity**
- Amyloporia lenis* f. *lunulispora* (Pilát) Bondartsev—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 179).
- Amyloporia xantha* f. *crassa* (Baxter) Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 154).
- Amyloporia xantha* var. *crassa* (Baxter)—Ulianishchev (1958: 76).
- Bjerkandera fumosa* f. *alba* (Fr.) Donk—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 428), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Ceraporina truncatus* (unpublished, or misprint?)—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Cerrena unicolor* f. *albida* Weinm.—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 285), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129).
- Chaetoporus subacidus* (Peck) Bondartsev & Singer—Kanygina (1964: 38, “on logs of *Fagus*!”). Possibly misidentified.
- Coriollus colliculosus* var. *saliciseda* Pilát—Bondarzew (1953: 518).
- Coriollus serialis* f. *ptychogaster* (“Mez”) Domański—Bondartseva & Seman (1978: 78), Bondartseva *et al.* (1981: 76).
- Corioloopsis gallica* f. *tenuis* Bourdot & Galzin—Kanygina (1964: 42), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403).
- Coriolus epileucus* (Fr.) Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 500), Kanygina (1964: 41), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Ganbarov *et al.* (1988: 106), Mukhamedshin (1989: 83, 2005: 236), Bondartseva (1998: 203), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 404), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). According to Ryvar den (1991), type of this taxon was lost.
- Coriolus fibula* (Fr.) Quél.—Sesli (2007: 80). Possibly a form of *Trametes hirsuta*, cf. *Coriolus hirsutus* var. *fibula* and *Polystictus fibula*; according to Bondarzew (1953: 489), all these taxa are synonymous.
- Coriolus hirsutus* f. *sulcatus* P. Karst.—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Coriolus hirsutus* var. *fibula* (Fr.) Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 489), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 290), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 431), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 97, 1999: 129), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). Cf. *Coriolus fibula*.
- Coriolus suaveolens* (Schumach.) Kumm.—Nanagulyan *et al.* (2002: 73). Possibly a misprint.
- Corticium woronowii* Bres.—Woronow (1915: 103), Melia *et al.* (1987: 454).
- Cristella mutabilis* var. *microspora* Parmasto—Parmasto (1965a: 223).
- Cristella sulphurea* var. *membranacea* Parmasto—Parmasto (1965a: 224).
- Cristella sulphurea* var. *pellicularis* Parmasto—Parmasto (1965a: 224).
- Fomes alni* (Sorokin) Sacc.—Woronow (1915: 116). According to Donk (1974: 284), this is a nomen dubium.
- Fomes fulvus* (Scop.) Fr.—Woronichin (1927: 156).
- Fomes igniarius* f. *resupinatus* Bres. in Bondartsev—Woronichin (1927: 156).
- Fomes nigrolaccatus* (Cooke) Sacc.—Solovjev (1932: 121).
- Fomitopsis officinalis* (Vill.) Bondartsev & Singer—Ryvar den & Gilbertson (1993: 261, on map). Not indicated by any other authors who have visited the Caucasus region.
- Fomitopsis unita* var. *lateritia* Bourdot & Galzin—Bondarzew (1953: 312).
- Funalia mollihirsuta* (misprint?)—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Ganoderma manoutchebrii* Steyaert—Steyaert (1972: 6), Hallenberg (1981: 497), Moradali *et al.* (2007: 264). Most probably conspecific with *Ganoderma pfeifferi* Bres.
- Ganoderma resinaceum* f. *quercinum* Dzhaf.—Kanygina (1972: 181, 1986: 46).
- Gloeoporus amorphus* f. *leucoporus* Bres.—Bondarzew (1953: 252).
- Gloeoporus amorphus* f. *molluscus* (P. Karst.) Bourdot & Galzin—Bondarzew (1953: 252).
- Gloeoporus amorphus* f. *vitreus* (Quél.) Bourdot & Galzin—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 434), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Haploporus ljubarskii* f. *conifer* Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 524).
- Himantia candida* (Huds.) Pers.—Melia *et al.* (1987: 260).

- Hirschioporus fragilis* Nikol.—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). The name with unknown application.
- Hirschioporus fuscoviolaceus* f. *lenzitoideus* (Murrill) Bondartsev—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 99).
- Hydnum schestunovii* Nikol.—Nikolajeva (1949b: 87).
- Irpex lacteus* f. *resupinata*—Singer (1931: 516). The name with unknown application.
- Irpex woronowii* Bres.—Woronow (1915: 111), Bondarzew (1953: 556), Nikolajeva (1953: 197, 1961: 307), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 436), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). According to Maas Geesteranus (1974: 503), this is not an *Irpex*.
- Lenzites lutescens* Syd.—Singer (1930: 78). A species described from Argentina, possibly misidentified. See Donk (1974: 332).
- Odontia diaphana* (Schrad.) Gray—Woronow (1915: 109), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 437), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Oidium decipiens* Sacc.—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Peniophora laevis* “Höhn. & Litsch.”—Woronow (1915: 104). Possibly *P. laevis* (Pers.) Burt = *Phanerochaete laevis* (Pers.) J. Erikss. & Ryvardeen?
- Phanerochaete rimosa* (Cooke) Burds. (= *Scopuloides rimosa* (Cooke) Jülich) – L—Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007). Most probably a synonym of *Scopuloides hydnoides*.
- Phanerochaete velutina* var. *cremicolor* Parmasto—Parmasto (1967: 389).
- Pbellinus igniarius* f. *resupinatus* Bourdot & Galzin—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 242), Simonyan (1981: 150).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *aceris* (Bourdot & Galzin) Pilát—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 254).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *corni* (Bourdot & Galzin) Pilát—Bondarzew (1953: 393), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 253), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *crataegi* (Bourdot & Galzin) Pilát—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *loniceriae* (Bourdot & Galzin) Pilát—Gulmagarashvili (1974: 418), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *piri* (Bourdot & Galzin) Pilát—Bondarzew (1953: 396); Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440); Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *quercus* (Bourdot & Galzin) Pilát—Bondarzew (1953: 395), Gulmagarashvili (1978: 685), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Pbellinus ribis* f. *rosae* (Jacz.) Pilát—Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 253), Kanygina (1986: 47), Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 93).
- Pbellinus robustus* f. *eucalypti* Bourdot & Galzin—Bondarzew (1953: 363).
- Pbellinus robustus* f. *robiniae* Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 364), Melik-Khachatryan & Martirosyan (1971: 245).
- Pbellinus robustus* f. *spiraeeae* Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 364), Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 440), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Podoporia sanguinolenta* f. *subexpallescens* (Bourdot & Galzin) Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 134).
- Polyporus albidus* “(W. F.) Fr.”—Melia *et al.* (1987: 18).
- Polyporus albus* (Huds.) Fr.—Woronow (1915: 118), Woronichin (1927: 157), Melia *et al.* (1987: 18), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Polyporus benzoinus* Fr. f. *resupinata* - Vasil’eva (1939: 38 found on a log of *Fagus*). Possibly *Ischnoderma resinum* (Schrad.) P. Karst.
- Polyporus cuticularis* b. *triqueter* Fr.—Buhse (1860: 245). Probably *Onnia triquetra* (Pers.) Imazeki.
- Polyporus nigrescens* Lasch—Rabenhorst (1871: 23), Saber (1974: 25). Possibly *Polyporus nigricans* Lasch in Rabenh., synonym of *Trametes versicolor* (see Donk 1974: 46).
- Polyporus podlachicus* Bres.—Melia *et al.* (1987: 187).
- Polyporus pseudobetulinus* (Murashk. ex Pilát) Thorn, Kotir. & Niemelä—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1999: 129). Possibly a misidentification.
- Polyporus tenuiparietalis* Bondartsev (nom. nudum)—Vasil’eva (1939: 40).
- Polyporus varius* f. *umbilicatus* (Pilát) Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 450).
- Polyporus varius* f. *undulatolobatus* (Bourdot & Galzin) Bondartsev—Bondarzew (1953: 450).
- Polyporus vulpinus* Fr. (= *Polystictus vulpinus* (Fr.) Cooke)—Hollós (1902: 149, 1905: 318), Filarszky (1907: 18), Woronow (1915: 120). Possibly *Inonotus rheades* (see Donk 1974: 95).
- Polystictus fibula* (Sowerby) Fr.—Woronow (1915: 120), Melia *et al.* (1987: 107). A tropical species. Probably a misidentified *Trametes hirsuta*.
- Polystictus lutescens* (Pers.) Fr.—Woronichin (1927: 158). Possibly *Trametes pubescens* (vide Donk 1974: 43).
- Poria ambigua* var. *albogilvus* Bourdot & Galzin—Vasil’eva (1939: 41).
- Poria calcea* (Fr.) Bres.—Vasil’eva (1939: 41).
- Poria vulgaris* f. *vitrea* Bourdot & Galzin—Vasil’eva (1939: 41).
- Radulum eichleri* Bres.—Woronow (1915: 110).
- Stereum luteobadium* (Fr.) Fr.—Hollós (1902: 148, 1905: 316), Filarszky (1907: 16), Woronow (1915: 107), Melia *et al.* (1987: 98). A tropical species, obviously misidentified.
- Stereum ochraceum* Lloyd—Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 444), Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).
- Stereum versicolor* (Sw.) Fr.—Rabenhorst (1871: 23), Woronow (1915: 107), Saber (1974: 16). Possibly a misidentified form of *Stereum hirsutum* or *S. ostrea*.
- Thelephora versicolor* var. *caucasica* Weinm.—Weinmann (1836: 383, 384). Possibly a form of *Stereum hirsutum* or *S. ostrea*.
- Trametes suaveolens* f. *gibbosiformis* Nikol.—Kanygina (1964: 41), Hüseyin & Selçuk (2001: 403).
- Trametes theae* Zimm.—Speshnev (1902: 72, 1904: 95).
- Tyromyces byssinus* (Pers.) Bondartsev nom. provisor.—Nanagulyan & Taslakhchyan (1991: 95). Possibly an *Antrodiella* species.

Ungulina inzengae (Fr.?)—Khabiri (1968: 138).

Xylodon versiporus f. *deformis* (Schrad.) Domański—
Nakhutsrishvili (1986: 445); Gvritishvili *et al.* (2007).

Concluding remarks

The checklist comprises 389 corticioid and 246 polypore species for the Caucasus region. Table 1 summarizes the number of corticioids and polypores for each country (see also Fig. 2). Of the total 635 species listed here, 74 are new to the whole area, and 25 new to Iran. The figures are necessarily biased by the extent of the efforts made in mycological surveys, with less information available from less visited areas. There are more collections in herbaria yet to be examined, which will certainly provide further information to supplement this checklist. Before expending more effort examining herbarium specimens, or making new inventories in the area, we felt it is necessary to summarize the current state-of-knowledge of these taxa in the Caucasus as a whole. We believe this will help to prioritize the allocation of time and resources on the rest of the material.

Where possible, we attempted to corroborate the literature reports with specimens examined by us. Within the time span of this study, however, we were not able to confirm the identifications in all published reports, and do not exclude the possibility of many misidentifications. The matters of special concern are old records which were not confirmed by recent observations. We recommend that the pertaining literature be treated more as a bibliographic source for the taxa than as a tool for drawing discrete conclusions. Reliable records can only be established when the respective or recent material is examined.

The ratio of polypores to corticioids in the Caucasus region is 1:1.6 (Table 1). The figure in some more Northern areas ranges between 1:2–1:7 (e.g. Knudsen *et al.* 1993; Penttilä & Kotiranta 1996; Kotiranta & Mukhin 2000; Kosonen & Huhtinen 2008; Kotiranta *et al.* 2009). There may be several factors important for such pattern, e.g. the difference in geography as well as amount, type and quality of habitats

Fig. 2. Diagram representing the proportion of corticioid and polypore species in the Caucasus region. Vertical scales represent the number of species.

can play role. Another point to consider is that our list is most probably shorter than the actual number of species present in this floristically rich area, part of which may be represented in data not available to us. We hope that this checklist will lead to more accurate surveys of the entire area and eventually to a joint Red List of aphylloporoid fungi including threat categories. It must also be noted that the regular updates on the checklist can be accessed in future via a website under construction.

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Table 1. The number of corticioid and polypore species in the Caucasus region^a

	Corticioids	Polypores	Total	Cort./Poly.
AR	100	126	226	0.8
AZ	87	99	186	0.9
GR	140	160	300	0.9
IRN	186	109	295	1.7
RUS	306	190	496	1.6
TUR	121	80	201	1.4
<i>W Transcaucasus</i>	23	0	23	na
Common to all	24	38	62	na
The Caucasus region	389	246	635	1.6

^a See the text for delimitation of the area and country abbreviations; na: not applicable.

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